

**RELEVANCE OF POPE FRANCIS' SOCIO-ECOLOGICAL THOUGHTS
FOR MAJOR AREAS OF SYSTEMATIC THEOLOGY**

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8 SEPTEMBER 2017**

The relevance of Pope Francis' socio-ecological thoughts for Sacramental Theology (The Sacrament of the Eucharist)

“The Sacraments are a privileged way in which nature is taken up by God to become a means of mediating supernatural life. Through our worship of God, we are invited to embrace the world on a different plane. Water, oil, fire and colors are taken up in all their symbolic power and incorporated in our act of praise”
(Pope Francis, *Laudato Si* 235)

The three points that I learned in the “Sacramental Theology” class may seem to be modest; however, these three points are key to an understanding of, and to approach the triad *God, humanity* and the *world*. These three points are: “Jesus Christ [the Son] is the sacrament of God [the Father]” (Cf. Colossians 1:15)¹, “The Church [that is, us] is the universal sacrament of salvation [in Christ]” (*LG* 48)², and the “The [created] world is the sacrament of God”. Additionally, I learned that “Nature is the primary revelation of God”. The theology of the sacrament that flows from these three points, therefore, has an ecological dimension. The ecological dimension is, of course, in addition to the wide variety of understandings of what sacramental theology is all about, its origins, necessity and importance in the Catholic life of the believers in the light of the Church’s teachings. In this paper, I will show the relevance of Pope Francis’ teachings on Sacramental Theology, especially on the Eucharist as presented in *Laudato Si’ (LS)*, which while in conformity with the Church’s magisterium teaching, simultaneously challenges to some extent this teaching.

Definition of the sacrament of Eucharist: To begin, although for some Catholics (including a few influential ones), Pope Francis is not faithful to the tradition of the Church, for others, such as Cardinal Donald Wuerl of the Archdiocese of Washington, Pope Francis is trying to reconnect the

¹ In this passage, Saint Paul said that “Jesus Christ is the visible image of the invisible God [then a sacrament of God] while Aquinas would say that, “[only] sensible things are required for the sacraments.” See Aquinas, *STh*, III, q. 64, a. 4 “*Respondeo*”. See also: Béguerie Philippe and Claude Duchesneau. *How to Understand the Sacraments*. New York: Crossroad, 1994, 173. For the two great theologians, “Christ is the sacrament of encounter with God.” Notice that for the entire work, I will be using the NABRE version of the Bible.

² *Lumen Gentium (LG)* In: http://www.vatican.va/archive/hist_councils/ii_vatican_council/documents/vat-ii_const_19641121_lumen-gentium_en.html, accessed on August 3rd, 2017. See: *Lumen Gentium* 1: “The Church, in Christ, is a kind of sacrament or sign of intimate union with God, and of unity of the whole human race.” See also: Leo Scheffczyk. “The Church as the Universal Sacrament of Jesus Christ.” *International Journal for the Study of the Christian Church* 10, no. 1 (February 2010): 18-45.

Church with the spirit of the Second Vatican Council³. Agreeing with the Cardinal, I assume that Pope Francis would approach the sacrament of the Eucharist in the way defined in the Catechism of the Catholic Church:

At the Last Supper, on the night he was betrayed, our Savior instituted the Eucharistic sacrifice of his **Body and Blood** [which is the **Real Presence**]. This he did in order to perpetuate the **sacrifice** of the cross throughout the ages until he should come again, and so to entrust to his beloved Spouse, the Church, a **memorial** of his death and resurrection: a sacrament of love, a sign of unity, a bond of charity, a **Paschal banquet [of joy]** in which Christ is consumed, the mind is filled with grace, and a pledge of future glory is given to us. (CCC 1323, emphasis added)⁴

This definition provides at least four ways to understand the Eucharist. These ways are suggested by the names that have been attributed to the Eucharist (i.e. a “memorial”, a “sacrifice”, a “banquet of joy”, the “Real Presence”). Additionally, the same definition helps not only to understand the pastoral (or practical) dimension of the sacrament, particularly in two ways. Firstly, the Eucharist is a ritual whose center is Christ that brings God’s people together and nourishes them along the journey toward God. John’s gospel recounts: “unless you eat the flesh of the Son of Man and drink his blood, you do not have life within you” (John 6:53). Second is to investigate more deeply the theological dimension of the sacrament as the “Real Presence of Christ” through his Body and his Blood, as the “Sacrifice”, as the “Memorial” and as the “Paschal Banquet” or “Banquet of joy”. Each name, as the CCC states, evokes a certain aspect of the sacrament. In order to fully understand the theology of the Eucharist, we should understand why each name is given to the sacrament.

³ Gerard O'Connell. *Cardinal Wuerl: Pope Francis has reconnected the church with Vatican II*. March 06, 2017, In: <https://www.americamagazine.org/faith/2017/03/06/cardinal-wuerl-pope-francis-has-reconnected-church-vatican-ii>, accessed on August 8th, 2017.

⁴ *Catechism of The Catholic Church*, in: http://www.vatican.va/archive/ccc_css/archive/catechism/p2s2c1a3.htm, accessed on July 8th, 2017, emphasis added. See also: the similar words in *Sacrosanctum Concilium* § 47, “At the Last Supper, on the night when He was betrayed, our Saviour instituted the eucharistic sacrifice of His **Body and Blood**. He did this in order to perpetuate the **sacrifice** of the Cross throughout the centuries until He should come again, and so to entrust to His beloved spouse, the Church, a **memorial** of His death and resurrection: a sacrament of love, a sign of unity, a bond of charity, a **paschal banquet** in which Christ is eaten, the mind is filled with grace, and a pledge of future glory is given to us”, emphasis added. For Aquinas, the sacrament of the Eucharist has a threefold name with regard to the past, the present and the future. These three names are: Sacrifice, Communion, Banquet. See: Aquinas, *STh*, III, q. 73, a. 4 “*Respondeo*”.

First, Eucharist is defined as a “Memorial”. Through this memorial, the Faithful make the past present. The past here refers to the Last Supper when “[Jesus] took the bread, said the blessing, broke it, and gave it to them, saying, “This is my body, which will be given for you; do this in memory of me.” (Lk 22:19) and did the same with the chalice of wine. In 1 Cor 11:24, Saint Paul used the word “remembrance” to refer to the sacrament as a memorial. The Eucharist aims to make the past present and points toward the future, as an anticipation of the heavenly banquet. Therefore, it has an eschatological dimension traditionally understood as an *already* and *not yet*.

Second, Eucharist is a “sacrifice” in the sense that Jesus’ Last Supper with the disciples is inseparable from the event of the cross. To illustrate this St. Paul stated, “Clear out the old yeast, so that you may become a fresh batch of dough, inasmuch as you are unleavened. For our paschal lamb, Christ, has been sacrificed. Therefore, let us celebrate the feast, not with the old yeast, the yeast of malice and wickedness, but with the unleavened bread of sincerity and truth” (1 Cor 5: 7-8). The unleavened bread here is connected to the festive dimension of the Eucharist as banquet of joy.

Third, the Eucharist is a “banquet of joy” that makes possible union in the Church through the person of Christ, who leads to “communion” or *koinonia* (Cf. *LG 22*)⁵. This aspect that was emphasized at the Second Vatican Council is very important and goes together with the sacrificial aspect of the Eucharist as the two sides of a same coin: Christ. Through the species of the bread and the wine, we are united with Christ. This helps to understand why St Paul asked these two important questions to the inhabitants of Corinth, “The cup of blessing that we bless, is it not a participation in the blood of Christ? The bread that we break, is it not a participation in the body of Christ?” (1 Cor 10:16). Our participation in the body and blood of Christ is called to be active. We do not go to mass just for the sake of attendance, but to fully participate in the celebration of the mystery. Moved

⁵ See also issues related to Contemporary Ecclesiology: Susan K. Wood. “The Church as Communion.” In: Peter C. Phan. *The gift of the Church* (Collegeville, Minnesota: The Liturgical Press, 2000) 162.

by the Spirit, we all (the celebrant, the congregation) should find ways to make the Mass something exciting, interesting and meaningful, using our creativity or talent. In my country, Haiti, the drum, which was initially used in the Voodoo celebration was introduced to the Mass after Vatican II and surprisingly gives more color and flavor to the mass. Celebrating the Eucharist is, in fact, celebrating the joy –this “living hope”– brought by the Resurrection of Christ”, as it states in the First Letter of Peter (Cf. 1 Pet 1: 3-9).

Fourth, the Eucharist is the “Real presence” of Christ through his Body and his Blood. This way for Christ being present to us is neither a metaphor nor a symbol⁶. The Real Presence of Christ is biblically founded in the Gospels and the Letter of St Paul, when the latter said, “and, after he had given thanks, broke it and said, “This is my body that is for you. Do this in remembrance of me.” In the same way also the cup, after supper, saying, “This cup is the new covenant in my blood. Do this, as often as you drink it, in remembrance of me.” (1 Cor 11:24:25). Pope Francis stated that, “It is in the Eucharist that all that has been created finds its greatest exaltation. Grace, which tends to manifest itself tangibly, found unsurpassable expression when God himself became man and gave himself as food for his creatures” (*LS* 236). In fact, the sacraments of the New Law, as Aquinas would say, are instrumental cause of grace⁷. Although the gift of this food to eat could appear to be “too hard, shocking and seemingly scandalous” and even misinterpreted as a “sort of cannibalism”, the Eucharist can be rightly referred to as “Passover of the New Covenant”. The body and the blood of Christ are very truly Christ Himself. There is no dichotomy between Christ and his body and blood. The document of the 2017 Synod of the Bishop stated that, the Lord has desired his Real

⁶ See: Baber, H. E. "The Real Presence." *Religious Studies* 49, no. 1 (2013): 19-33.

⁷ See: Aquinas, *STh*, III, q. 62, a. 3 “*Respondeo*”.

Presence in the Blessed Sacrament so that God-Emmanuel might be, today and always, a God near to humanity as its Redeemer and Lord⁸.

Origin of the Eucharist: The origin of the Eucharist is in the scene of the Last Supper which pre-figured the scene of the Passover. This origin could be pre-figured in some of the episodes of the Old Testament. First, it refers to the Jewish Passover when the Lord commanded to Moses to “Tell the whole community of Israel: On the tenth of this month *every family must procure for itself a lamb*, one apiece for each household”. The Lord continued to tell him, “If a household is too small for a lamb, it along with its nearest neighbor will procure one, and apportion the lamb’s cost in proportion to the number of persons, according to what each household consumes” (Ex. 12:3-4). In this second part, there was a sense of celebrating altogether as family. Secondly, it refers to the Manna in the desert, when the Lord said to Moses, “I am going to rain down bread from heaven for you. Each day the people are to go out and gather their daily portion” (Ex. 16:4). Finally, it has to do with the Bread of the Presence whose recipe was as follows, “You shall take bran flour and bake it into twelve cakes, using two tenths of an ephah of flour for each cake. These you shall place in two piles, six in each pile, on the pure gold table before the Lord. With each pile put some pure frankincense, which shall serve as an *oblation to the Lord*, a token of *the bread offering*” (Lev. 24:5-7; Cf. Ex. 25:23-24; 29-30). Although all of those scenes exemplify what Pope Francis says about the origin of the Eucharist which is Jesus Christ Himself, “[that] comes not from above, but from within, he comes that we might find him in this world of ours” (LS 236). Those scenes could be considered as prefiguration of the sacrament of the Eucharist that has its origin in the new covenant brought by Christ and fulfilled in him.⁹

⁸ See the Synod of Bishops. XI Ordinary General Assembly the Eucharist: Source and Summit of the Life and Mission of the Church, In: http://www.vatican.va/roman_curia/synod/documents/rc_synod_doc_20040528_lineamenta-xi-assembly_en.html, accessed on August 3rd, 2017: §c.

⁹ For Walsh, “The rite of the Eucharist is, even in its present form, highly complex. Its history is correspondingly complex.” See: Liam G. Walsh. *Sacraments of Initiation, Second Edition: A Theology of Life, Word, and Rite* (Chicago: Hillenbrand Books, 2011) Kindle Locations 4322-4323. Kindle Edition.

Necessity of the Eucharist: The statement “no salvation outside of the Church” is well-known but often misunderstood. The Church is connected to the sacrament of the Eucharist in the sense that there is no salvation outside of Christ who is the “primordial sacrament of salvation”. This could explain why the “*sacrament is necessary*” for those who attain the age of reason and are aware of its profound meaning¹⁰. This necessity is important. It leads us to better understand why those who approach the Table should be in state of grace. Otherwise, they should go to confession in order to have their sins forgiven, “I will give you [Peter] the keys to the kingdom of heaven. Whatever you bind on earth shall be bound in heaven; and whatever you loose on earth shall be loosed in heaven.” (Matthew 16:19). Pope Francis would argue that: “Everyone can share in some way in the life of the church; everyone can be part of the community, nor should the doors of the sacraments be closed for simply any reason” (*Evangelii Gaudium* 47). Celebrating the Eucharist is synonymous with celebrating a banquet in which the joy and the life brought by the Risen Lord prevails over the sadness that is brought by his Passion and his death. With a deep understanding of this, youths and young Catholic families would not think the Eucharist as a kind of wearisome, tiresome or boring activity. Rather, “the Eucharist is itself an act of cosmic love: “Yes, cosmic! Because even when it is celebrated on the humble altar of a country church, the Eucharist is always in some way celebrated on the altar of the world” (*LS* 236) not on that of a specific Church among the churches”. The Eucharist has an ecumenical value. It also has an ecological value, as Pope Francis continued saying that, “[it] is a source of light and motivation for our concerns for the environment [and that of the poor], directing us to be stewards of all creation” (*LS* 236).

Importance of the Eucharist: The main purpose of the sacrament of Eucharist is according to the Church’s teachings nourishing the people of God not only through faith, but also by words and

¹⁰ Cf. Aquinas, *STh*, III, q. 61, a. 1 “Respondeo”, with emphasis added.

concrete actions (Cf. *SSC* 59)¹¹. Because the nourishment that the Eucharist provides heals and sanctifies those who receive it, it is essential for salvation as the Evangelist Saint John acknowledges when he said, “Whoever eats my flesh and drinks my blood has eternal life, and *I will raise him on the last day.*” (John 6:64). At this theological level, the Eucharist is Jesus given to us as the “Heavenly Bread” that will nourish us along our earthly journey¹². Although the assumption that all the sacraments abide in Christ remains valid, the person of Christ Himself –through His body and blood– is not only *at* the heart of the sacrament of the Eucharist but also, *He is* the Eucharist. This gives a special character to the sacrament of Eucharist and makes it “the source and summit of Christian life” (*LG* 11). Refusing the Eucharist under the species of the bread and wine is categorically refusing Christ, as Christ is *real, true* and *substantial*. However, Christ is more than the species of bread and the wine as, “In the Eucharist, fullness is already achieved; Christ is the living center of the all universe, the overflowing core of love and of inexhaustible life” (*LS* 236).

Although many (Catholics and non-Catholics) recognize the Eucharist as a sacrament, there still are many differences in the way that they interpret and welcome their faith. For the Catholics, the Eucharist is the Real Presence of Christ. In other words, it is a nourishment that cannot perish. After the celebration, this “presence” under the species of the bread and the wine should be conserved and is worthy to be adored. Does Eucharist deal with sins? The response is “yes” because Christ is operative in it and through Him, “God will fully supply whatever you need, in accord with his glorious riches in Christ Jesus (Philippians 4:19). Although the primary effect of the sacrament of the Eucharist is not dealing with sins as the sacrament of Baptism does for original sin particularly and as the sacrament of Confession does for the actual (or personal) sins of the

¹¹ This could be applied for the sacraments in general. See: Second Vatican Council. Constitution of the Sacred Liturgy *Sacrosanctum Concilium (SSC)*, 1963, In: www.vatican.va, accessed on July 23rd, 2017.

¹² For Vorgrimler Herber, the Eucharist also has a healing effect on those who receive it. See: Vorgrimler Herbert, *Sacramental Theology* (Minnesota: The Liturgical Press, 1992) 162. This idea was already present in Denzinger-Schonmetzer (DS) 1320-1322.

believers. However, because the Scripture said that, “where sin increased, grace [that we all receive from God through Jesus] overflowed all the more” (Rm 5:20). Eucharist strengthens us and improve our relationship with God. In *Evangelii Gaudium*, Pope Francis puts in this way, “The Eucharist, although it is the fullness of sacramental life, is not a prize for the perfect but a powerful medicine and nourishment for the weak” (*Evangelii Gaudium* 47).

The *Canon Law Code* states that, “The Christian faithful [that is the Catholics] have the right to receive assistance from the sacred pastors out of the spiritual goods of the Church, especially the word of God and the sacraments” (c. 213). In that context, Christians have some obligations towards the Church: celebrating the sacraments in order to fully exercise their right. It is relevant, however, to know that some Churches not in communion with the Roman Catholic Church (the Lutheran Church as an example), besides the sacrament of Baptism, considers the sacrament of the Eucharist as sacrament because it is based on Jesus’ command to the disciples during the Last Supper, “While they were eating, Jesus took bread, said the blessing, broke it, and giving it to his disciples said, “Take and eat; this is my body.” Then he took a cup, gave thanks, and gave it to them, saying, “Drink from it, all of you, for this is my blood of the covenant, which will be shed on behalf of many for the forgiveness of sins” (Mt 26:26-28).

The challenge brought by Pope Francis’ Laudato Si’: From the biblical passage of Jesus’ command, we can understand a few things. First, they were eating (maybe having an ordinary meal) before Jesus gave a specific tone to the second meal (the Eucharistic meal) and instituted it as a sacrament. However, the Son of God, Jesus Christ, through his actions at the Last Supper and particularly his words “Do this in Memory of me,” did not intend simply to institute a fraternal meal but a liturgy, a true act of worship and adoration of the Father “in spirit and in truth” (John 4:24), as

stated in the Church Document from the Synod of Bishops on the Eucharist.¹³ Second, Jesus announces his Paschal sacrifice in an implicit way, as if He was saying to them: “See you in the banquet that will take place in the kingdom of Heaven”. This is the sense of the word “new” that is found in the previous passage. For in the sacrament of the Eucharist, we can see *explicitly* the words from the mouth of Jesus that constitute the form (or “formula” as the term appears in the book of the Canon Law) associated with the bread and the wine as the two requirements for the sacrament of Eucharist to be valid. However, Pope Francis would argue that, “Christians are called to accept the world [and all its riches] as a sacrament of communion [as a Eucharistic celebration or], as a way of sharing with God and our neighbors on a global scale. It is our humble conviction that the divine and the human meet in the slightest detail in the seamless garment of God’s creation, in the last speck of dust of our planet” (LS 9). This understanding of the world as a sacrament challenges the traditional way of thinking of the sacrament of communion or the Eucharist – under the “humble” species of the bread and wine.

To conclude, any baptized who reaches the age of reason could receive the sacrament of the Eucharist (Cf. c. 912). This means that encountering God – through the Eucharist – requires from us to be aware of Jesus Christ’ gaze. As one of the “sacraments of the new covenant”, Christ instituted the Eucharist the day before his Passion. Joined to Him, as the incarnate Son of God present in the Eucharist, the whole cosmos gives thanks to God (Cf. LS 236). All the Faithful believers of the Church of Christ (I mean, not only the Catholic Church) are highly encouraged to understand the intent of the sacrament of Eucharist in order to live it in a festive way, not like those “hypocrites”

¹³ See: Synod of Bishops. XI Ordinary General Assembly. *The Eucharist: Source and Summit of the Life and Mission of the Church* (28 May 2004), In: http://www.vatican.va/roman_curia/synod/documents/rc_synod_doc_20040528_lineamenta-xi-assembly_en.html, accessed on August 3rd, 2017.

who look gloomy while fasting (Mt 6:16)¹⁴. Rather, being —as Jesus Christ among us— a “Eucharistic presence” that brings energy, joy and hope for the world.¹⁵

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¹⁴ Although Eucharist in the Catholic Church has a theological foundation and the faithful Christians are invited to “[adhere] to the teaching of the Holy Scriptures, to the apostolic traditions, and to the consensus . . . of the Fathers” (CCC 1114) and that Catholics believe that Christ remains in the host even after the mass is ended. This is different for some non-Catholic Churches. See: Aquinas, *STh*, III, q. 77, a. 4 “Respondeo.”

¹⁵ Being a “sacramental presence” in this context here means being capable with the grace that we receive to love and to serve. It is also being ready to sacrifice oneself (as Christ has done) for the sake of others (and in the name of the same Christ). See: Juan Luis Segundo, *The Sacraments Today* (New York: Orbis Books, 1974) 132. His point is rooted in the First Epistle of Peter (1 Pet 1: 3-9).

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The relevance of Pope Francis' socio-ecological thoughts for Christology

“The world was created by the three Persons acting as a single divine principle, but each one of them performed this common work in accordance with his own personal property. Consequently, “when we contemplate with wonder the universe in all its grandeur and beauty, we must praise the whole Trinity”
(Pope Francis, *Laudato Si* 169)

In the previous chapter, we explored the theology of the sacraments that flows from the triad of *God, humanity* and the *world* and we recalled the statement “Jesus Christ [the Son] is the sacrament of God [the Father]” (Cf. Colossians 1:15).¹⁶ The theology of Christ from the perspective of *who Christ is* (Christology) or *what Christ does* (Soteriology) flows from Trinitarian theology, which in its turn has an ecological, ecclesial and ecumenical component. In the present paper, I shall explore and focus on the person of Christ from among the three Persons that created the world. Knowing that Christ is inscribed in the context of the Trinitarian Theology, I shall show the relevance of Pope Francis' teachings on Christology and soteriology.

The Trinity: In his social Encyclical Letter *Laudato Si'*, Pope Francis outlines his understanding of the persons of the Trinity, showing succinctly and respectively what Abbatology, Christology and Pneumatology are all about. According to him,

The Father is the ultimate source of everything, the loving and self-communicating foundation of all that exists. The Son [Jesus Christ], his reflection, through whom all things were created, united himself to this earth when he was formed in the womb of Mary. The Spirit, infinite bond of love, is intimately present at the very heart of the universe, inspiring and bringing new pathways (*LS* 238).

Pope Francis' understanding of the Trinity, as we can see, is not something new, as he recognizes that “The mystery of the Most Holy Trinity is the central mystery of the Christian faith and of Christian life. God alone can make it known to us by revealing himself as Father, Son and Holy Spirit” (*CCC* 261). We can believe the mystery of God One and Triune only through faith. This

¹⁶ In this passage, Saint Paul said that “Jesus Christ is the visible image of the invisible God [then a sacrament of God] while Aquinas would say that, “[only] sensible things are required for the sacraments.” See Aquinas, *STh*, III, q. 64, a. 4 “*Respondeo*.” See also: Béguerie Philippe and Claude Duchesneau. *How to Understand the Sacraments* (New York: Crossroad, 1994) 173. For the two great theologians, “Christ is the sacrament of encounter with God.”

mystery is relevant for the ecumenical dialogue (and even the interfaith dialogue) because, “It is a mystery that finds its highest exemplar and source in the unity of the Persons of the Trinity: The Father and the Son and the Holy Spirit, one God” (*Unitatis Redintegratio* 2). However, when Pope Francis says, “The world was created by the three Persons acting as a single divine principle, but each one of them performed this common work in accordance with his own personal property” (*LS* 238), he clearly comes with a “new” understanding of the Trinity as the Creator of the world.

New understanding, new challenges: Pope Francis’ understanding of the Triune God as Creator, in fact, challenges the traditional way of thinking of the Father as the Creator, the Son as the Savior and the Holy Spirit as the Sanctifier. The act of creation has been the *distinctive* mission of the Father (Cf. *CCC* 190)¹⁷. Pope Francis wants to change this way of thinking about (and even sensing) the Most Holy Trinity, and his desire (I am convinced) is that, “when we contemplate with wonder the universe in all its grandeur and beauty, we must praise the whole Trinity [not *only* and *exclusively* the Father]” (*LS* 238). My attention in this paper is on the second person of the Trinity, “[Jesus] Christ, true God and true man, [who] has a human intellect and will, perfectly attuned and subject to his divine intellect and divine will, which he has in common with the Father and the Holy Spirit” (*CCC* 482). Jesus Christ – the Son of God – has to be seen in relation with the two other persons: The Father and the Holy Spirit.

Christology and Soteriology: The *Catechism of the Catholic Church* recognizes the “Incarnation [of Jesus Christ as] the mystery of the wonderful union of the divine and human natures in the one person of the Word” (*CCC* 483). For many theologians two things are important to understand in the person of Jesus Christ: his nature (or identity) and his mission. Although those

¹⁷ The *CCC* recognizes that “The Creed is divided into three parts: “the first part speaks of the first divine Person [the Father] and the wonderful work of creation; the next speaks of the second divine Person [the Son] and the mystery of his redemption of men; the final part speaks of the third divine Person [the Holy Spirit], the origin and source of our sanctification.” These are “the three chapters of our [baptismal] seal”, In: www.vatican.va.

two things are not separable, some theologians distinguish *what Jesus* is from *what he says or does*. For the former, they attribute the name of “Christology” while for the later, they attribute the name of “soteriology”. The certitude about the use of these terms is that they are not making any reference to the Father and to the Holy Spirit. According to Edward Schillebeeckx, an eminent Dutch theologian, “Jesus Christ is the sacrament of the encounter with God”¹⁸. This statement has its foundation in Pauline Theology that sees in Jesus the visible image of the invisible God (Colossians 1:15).

The Christ of the Gospel: Pope Francis’ approach to Christology is mainly biblical, and it seems to me that the Holy Father desires to polish and expand our image of the God of Abraham, Isaac and Jacob. The Divine Persons show us that God acts throughout history (e.g. the people of Israel). The Trinity can be a helpful image from which to approach social justice. The love (or “mercy”) that exists between the Father, the Son and the Holy Spirit involves the history of the entire humanity into their love and transforms the world regardless its brokenness. According to Pope Francis, “The name of [the Triune] God is mercy,”¹⁹ and this mercy of the Father is fully revealed through the Son. To illustrate *what Jesus did* (soteriology), Pope Francis refers to three parables of the Gospel among many other things: Jesus’ self-revelation as the love (or even better “mercy”) of God in “The Good Samaritan”²⁰ (Lk 10:25-37), “The Prodigal Son” (or better “The Merciful Father” as some wish, Lk 15: 11-32)²¹ and “The Good Shepherd” (John 11:1-18) with “the

¹⁸ Edward Schillebeeckx. *Christ, the Sacrament of the Encounter with God* (New York: Sheed and Ward, 1963) 13. In page 18, the author goes even further saying that “Christ is the norm and the source of every encounter with God.” See also: John Hart. *Sacramental Commons: Christian Ecological Ethics* (Maryland: Rowman & Littlefield Publishers, 2006). Kindle Location 217. Kindle Edition.

¹⁹ Francis, Andrea Torielli, and Oonagh Stransky. *The Name of God Is Mercy* (New York: Random House, 2016). Kindle Location 186. Kindle Edition.

²⁰ Pope Francis. *General Audience*. 27 April 2016 (Considerations on the Parable of the Good Samaritan), In: https://w2.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/audiences/2016/documents/papa-francesco_20160427_udienza-generale.html, accessed on August 24, 2017.

²¹ Pope Francis. *General Audience*. 11 May 2016 (Considerations on the Parable of the Prodigal Son), In: https://w2.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/audiences/2016/documents/papa-francesco_20160511_udienza-generale.html, accessed on August 24, 2017.

odor of sheep”²². For Pope Francis, the Lord of the Old Testament and the Lord of the New Testament are the same shepherd. Jesus came to reveal to us the true face or image of the Father who, in his great mercies, did not make an end of his people or forsake them, for he is a gracious and merciful God (Cf. Nehemiah 9:31).

Sources of Pope Francis’ Christology: Pope Francis’ audiences and homilies (even many of those delivered before his ascent to the See of Peter) may be found on the Vatican’s webpage and these serve as great resources in understanding the Pope’s Christology, regarding what Christ *is* and *does*. His audiences and/or homilies are significant means of communicating to the people of God. Through them we are capable of building a Christology that reflects Pope Francis’ socio-ecological teaching. According to David L. Gray, there are two reasons that could explain the relevance of Pope Francis’ homilies. The first reason is because of their Papal status of being non-Magisterial and informal utterances of a Pontiff. The second reason is because homiletic preaching during the audience is Pope Francis’ most frequent means of communicating with the faithful²³. Through Pope Francis’ homilies (which have a strong focus on the God’s mercy) demonstrate his ecclesial disposition is all about, especially when he recalls Francis of Assisi saying, “My mission as Pope is to repair my Church in ruins.”²⁴ In other words, one might put it in this way, Jesus’ coming into human history was fundamentally an act of love for the salvation of the entire God’s creation (human and non-human). God and his people are intimately connected through Jesus Christ, as “the one and only mediator between God and men” (CCC 480).

²² Pope Francis. *General Audience*. 4 May 2016 (considerations on the Parable of the Good Shepherd), In: https://w2.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/audiences/2016/documents/papa-francesco_20160504_udienza-generale.html, accessed on August 24, 2017.

²³ Cf. David L. Gray. “The Homiletic Christology of Pope Francis Regarding the Ongoing Mission of Christ Jesus” (28 May 2015), In: <http://www.saintdominicsmedia.com/christology-pope-francis/>, accessed on August 24th, 2017.

²⁴ Here Pope Francis refers to Francis of Assisi’s statement in Catholic Online 14 March 2013. See: Julie Schwieter Collazo and Lisa Rogak (ed.). *Pope Francis in His Own Words* (California: New World Library, 2013) 46.

The presence of the merciful Lord in the OT: The Pre-incarnate Christ: The title “Lord” has been used to designate the God of both the Old and the New Testament. However, it is quite interesting to see that this title mostly refers to the power of God (and not to “weak” one). The goodness of God, as portrayed in the Old Testament, is most of the time problematic considering facts such as expelling Adam and Eve from the garden of Eden (Genesis 2:4-3:24), the flood at the time Noah (Genesis 5:32-10:1), and the regret he had (Genesis 6:6). However, when it comes to look at him through the lenses of mercy things might change, “I [God] have observed the misery of my people who are in Egypt; I have heard their cry on account of their taskmasters. Indeed, I know their sufferings, and I have come down to deliver them... so I will send you...” (Ex 3:7-8, 10). Jesus Christ's coming through his humiliation and exultation reveals us the identity of the God of Israel (or the God of the Old testament, if you wish). Jesus Christ –as the God of the New Covenant– fulfills what has been written in the Hebrew Bible (or *Tanakh*), that is, the *Law* and the *Prophets* and the *Psalms* about God of Israel (usually pictured as God the Father)²⁵. Jesus Christ, the Son of God, reveals the face of God the Father in a very categorical way: mercy. Pope Francis would even say that, “Jesus Christ is the face of the Father’s mercy” (*Misericordiae Vultus* 1). These words might well sum up the mystery of God’s mercy. Since the beginning, God the Father, our Lord, was patient and merciful, as it is found in the books of the *Law* “[The LORD is] slow to anger and abounding in steadfast love, forgiving iniquity and transgression, but he will by no means clear the guilty, visiting the iniquity of the fathers on the children, to the third and the fourth generation” (Numbers 14:18; see also Exodus 34:6) and in the books of the *Prophets*, “Nevertheless, in your great mercies you did not make an end of them or forsake them, for you are a gracious and merciful God” (Nehemiah 9:31; see also Joel 2:13) and also in the book of the *Psalms*

²⁵ Here I want to recall what Jesus says to the disciples in Luke’s gospel about the presence (and even heritage) of Hebrew *Tanakh*, “These are my words that I spoke to you while I was still with you, that everything written about me in the **law** of Moses and in the **prophets** and **psalms** must be fulfilled” (Luke 24:44).

(or Psalter), “[...] you, O Lord, are a God merciful and gracious, slow to anger and abounding in steadfast love and faithfulness” (Ps 86:15). Pope Francis wants remind us this face of the Father who loves us so much when he says that, “In the “fullness of time” (Gal 4:4), when everything had been arranged according to his plan of salvation, he sent his only Son into the world, born of the Virgin Mary, to reveal his love for us in a definitive way. Whoever sees Jesus sees the Father (cf. Jn 14:9). Jesus of Nazareth, by his words, his actions, and his entire person reveals the mercy of God” (*Misericordiae Vultus* 1).

The presence of the merciful Lord in the New Testament: The incarnate Christ: The washing of the Feet of the disciples [considered as the biblical foundation of servant leadership] is one of the beautiful images of the New Testament that Pope Francis uses to show that the leader is the one who comes not to be served but to serve. His service is made possible because of his merciful nature exemplified “in his many actions throughout the history of salvation where his goodness prevails over punishment and destruction [...] “He forgives all our iniquity, he heals all our diseases, he redeems our life from the pit, he crowns us with steadfast love and mercy” (Ps 103:3-4)”. Pope Francis continues to show some of the concrete signs of the Lord’s mercy, using the words of the psalmist when he says, “[The Lord] executes justice for the oppressed; he gives food to the hungry. The Lord sets the prisoners free; the Lord opens the eyes of the blind. The Lord lifts up those who are bowed down; the Lord loves the righteous. The Lord watches over the sojourners, he upholds the widow and the fatherless; but the way of the wicked he brings to ruin” (Ps 146:7-9)” (*Misericordiae Vultus* 6). Jesus Christ came to perform the works of mercy and “[he] is the same yesterday [as pre-incarnate], today, and forever” (Hebrews 13:8). Because of Jesus is so good to us we “Give thanks to him, bless his name; good indeed is the Lord” (Psalm 100:5), knowing that “His mercy endures forever, his faithfulness lasts through every generation”.

Christology and Mission: One of Christ's most common title is *Messiah*, which means savior. His mission which is the mission of the Trinity is clearly revealed through his name or identity. When Peter has to respond to the question: Who Jesus is? This was his answer: "You are the Messiah (which means Christ), the Son of the Living God." In other words, as the Messiah, Jesus is the one who comes to perform the work of mercy even if the cost is to die for those he loves. As human beings, we all need the mercy that Jesus has brought and, "Only someone who has encountered mercy, who has been caressed by the tenderness of mercy, is happy and comfortable with God"²⁶. A little mercy makes the world less cold and more just"²⁷. "Mercy is the Lord's most powerful message" in the New as well in the Old Testament. It's not easy to trust oneself to the mercy of God, because his mercy is an unfathomable abyss- but we must do it"²⁸. This is why, "If the Lord did not forgive everything, the world would not exist"²⁹. Jesus wants to teach us [as Church] another way: "Go out! Go out! Share your testimony [of mercy], go out and interact with your brothers, go out and share, go out and ask! Become the Word in body as well as in spirit"³⁰. The Church is called to be missionary, carrier of the Gospel of the merciful Jesus Christ to all people, especially to those in the margins. There is here for the Church a strong sense of following and imitating Christ's missionary endeavor and call to be merciful as the Father (cf. Luke 6: 36).

Some systematic Interrelations: Pope Francis said that everything is interrelated (*LS* 120; 137; 138). Christ is the bond between the Father Creator and the created. Christ is at the heart of the sacraments of the Church, which are also interrelated. This is why they are also called "sacraments

²⁶ Pope Francis. *Homily*, In: National Catholic Reporter, 3 March 2013.

²⁷ "Mercy is in reality the core of the Gospel", says Pope Francis. See: Pope Francis. *Homily*. 17 March 2013, In: www.vatican.va. See the text also in: Julie Schwieter Collazo and Lisa Rogak (ed.). *Pope Francis in His Own Words* 46.

²⁸ Pope Francis. *Homily*. 17 March 2013, In: www.vatican.va. See the text also in: Julie Schwieter Collazo and Lisa Rogak (ed.). *Pope Francis in His Own Words* 46.

²⁹ Pope Francis. *Homily*. 17 March 2013, In: www.vatican.va. See the text also in: Julie Schwieter Collazo and Lisa Rogak (ed.). *Pope Francis in His Own Words* 46.

³⁰ Pope Francis. *Homily*, In: New York Daily News, 14 March 2013.

of the New Covenant”. Christ is in them as he is in all things. The Catechism of Catholic Church teaches us that, through Baptism we are initiated into the life, death and resurrection of Jesus Christ and incorporated into the Church (CCC 1213; See also John 13: 8). Through the Eucharist, Christ is revealing himself as the Real Presence (Matthew 26:26). This is what the Eucharist is: Christ’s Body and Blood. In Confession, Christ desires that we nourish good relationship with God, with himself, with one another (as humans) and with the entire creation. This is what Reconciliation, or Confession, means to be. According to Adrienne von Speyr’s approach on Sacramental Theology, the Eucharist has a Christological value (Christ’s *being*) while the Confession has a soteriological value (Christ’s *doing*). This is clearly what she means when she states, “Communion is what Christ is, Confession is what he did”³¹. What Christ –the *Messiah*– is (as Savior of the world) has been revealed in what he has done (Saving the world). Eucharist is to some extent the celebration of our reconciliation with God through Christ, and with one another as created beings. Therefore, the entire creation is concerned in the process of reconciliation, healing and peace.

Christ is living in our “common home”: Notice that this reconciliation happens in our “common home,” which the Pope understands as creation is where God is at work. The Christological dimension of Pope Francis’ main encyclical, *Laudato Si’*, can be drawn considering Christ as one among us who worthily shares our “common home” with us, “Christ has taken unto himself this material world and now, risen, is intimately present to each being, surrounding it with his affection and penetrating it with his light” (LS 221). As a result, this aspect of penetrating the material world has its origin in the Prologue of the Evangelist Saint John, especially from the specific passage that summarizes the incarnation into the world of Jesus Christ, the Word of God, “And the Word became flesh and made his dwelling among us, and we saw his glory, the glory as of the Father’s only Son, full of grace and truth” (John 1:14). Because Jesus becomes one of us,

³¹ Von Speyr. *Be* 104. See this text in: Matthew Lewis Sutton. *Heaven Opens: The Trinitarian Mysticism of Adrienne von Speyr* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2014) 22.

similar with the members of the created world in all things excepted in sin (as St Paul points it out in Hebrew 4:15; *Gaudium et Spes* 22), with us Jesus dwells in our “common home”³². Jesus Christ is, according to Pope Francis, the “One Person of the Trinity entered into the created cosmos” (*LS* 99)³³. Does that mean the Father and the Holy Spirit do not have anything to do with the created cosmos? “No”, I would say, and the reason is because the three divine persons Father, Son and Holy Spirit are always acting together. This is why the Catechism of the Catholic Church stresses that, “Inseparable in what they are, the divine persons are also inseparable in what they do” (*CCC* 267). This dogma leaves room to reconcile the tradition and the new way of thinking about the mission of the three persons of the Trinity as Creator, Savior and Sanctifier of the world or creation, and as Christians we must see ourselves as part of the Trinitarian missions³⁴. The dogma continues to say that “Within the single divine operation each shows forth what is proper to him in the Trinity, especially in the divine missions of the Son's Incarnation and the gift of the Holy Spirit” (*CCC* 267). The understanding of the work of the Trinity as a “team work” in creation, salvation and sanctification of the entire creation (I would say) is relevant for Ecclesiology, Interfaith and Ecumenism at both a theological and pastoral levels.

Christ, humanity and the other creatures: The St Paul says that, “Through him [as the word of God and pre-existent Christ], heavens and earth were created” (Colossians 1:16; See also John

³² The expression “common home” is used in a broader context and refers not only to the “earth” but the entire “creation” (that is, “heavens and earth are full of your glory” from the biblical perspective). In a similar way, Jesus dwells also in the tabernacle and reveals himself as the Real Presence *par excellence*. See: Adelaide Mary Abraham. *Christ's Real Presence in the Tabernacle and in the World* (Indiana: AuthorHouse, 2015) 22.

³³ Although Jesus was the incarnate one, as the initiative of creating the humanity (“Let us make humankind”), the initiative of saving humankind (“Let us perform the redemption of humankind”) was part of the discernment of the Trinity (as if it was a team work). See: The Meditation on Incarnation (SE 313-327), In: “Ignatius, and George E. Ganss. Ignatius of Loyola: *The Spiritual Exercises and Selected Works* (New York: Paulist Press, 1991)”.

³⁴ Besides the “visible mission” of the Son, Crowe will argue about the “invisible mission” of the Holy Spirit that strengthen us in our journey. See: Frederick Crowe. “Son of God, Holy Spirit and World Religions, In: *Appropriating the Lonergan Idea* (Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 2006) 324-343. See in connection to this, the section about “The joint mission of the Son and the Spirit” *CCC* 689-690. However, authors (such as Gregory Palamas) from the Eastern Church would interpret this union with God as a sort of “theosis” or “deification.” See also: Norris, F. W. “Deification: Consensual and Cogent,” *Scottish Journal of Theology* 43/4 (1996), 411-28.

1:3); however, through the care of humanity “[A]ll creatures are moving forward with us and through us towards a common point of arrival, which is God, in that transcendent fullness where the risen Christ embraces and illumines all things” (LS 83). This common point of arrival is the omega point (that is, Christ himself) of Teilhard de Chardin who, considering that our origin (the alpha point) and destiny (the omega point) is God stated that, “We are not human beings having a spiritual experience, but we are spiritual beings having a human experience.”³⁵ “In this universe, shaped by open and intercommunicating systems, we can discern countless forms of relationship and participation” (LS 79).

Interrelation between Christology and Ethics: A change of heart is important to our spiritual growth. In order to be and act like Jesus, knowing that, “What [we] all need is an ‘ecological conversion’, whereby the effects of their encounter with Jesus Christ become evident in their relationship with the world around them. Living our vocation to be protectors of God’s handiwork [that is, the creation] is essential to a life of virtue; it is not an optional or a secondary aspect of our Christian experience” (LS 217). The way we live our faith in everyday situation is a direct result of the content of our belief. If I believe in a merciful Triune God, I am invited to be merciful and even to accept the challenge that comes with it. Appropriating an ethics of mercy that includes each created item taken individually and the creation as a whole is important. There is a spirituality that flows the ecology, which pays greater attention to the preservation of the world as “a community of created realities” (I would say). Conscious of that, says Pope Francis, “I would like to offer Christians a few suggestions for an ecological spirituality grounded in the convictions of our faith, since the teachings of the Gospel have direct consequences for our way of thinking, feeling and living. More than in ideas or concepts as such, I am interested in how such a spirituality can motivate us to a more passionate concern for the protection of our world” (LS 216). He continues

³⁵ See: Arnaud Saint-Paul. *The Human Project* (Miami: Tapuat Publishing, 2011) 22.

saying that, “Christians have not always appropriated and developed the spiritual treasures bestowed by God upon the Church, where the life of the spirit is not dissociated from the body or from nature or from worldly realities, but lived in and with them, in communion with all that surrounds us” (*LS* 216). Being aware of how important it is to be considerate in the way we make use of things that we need, “Christian spirituality proposes a growth marked by moderation and the capacity to be happy with little. It is a return to that simplicity which allows us to stop and appreciate the small things, to be grateful for the opportunities which life affords us” (*LS* 222). “To be spiritually detached from what we possess, and not to succumb to sadness for what we lack, for Pope Francis, implies avoiding the dynamic of dominion and the mere accumulation of pleasures”.

For Pope Francis, Jesus Christ is [the Shepherd] who came to accompany us [as the sheep] on the journey of life (Cf. *LS* 235). Jesus is one of us. He is “someone” or “something” that we might feel either close to us or not, but He is always this “someone” or “something” near to us. This is probably why, for Pope Francis, “Encountering God does not mean fleeing from this world [around us] or turning our back on nature. It is instead “finding God all things” that have been given to us through the gift of creation itself. This is especially clear in the spirituality of the Christian East” (*LS* 235). Being aware of the divine intervention in creatures, Pope Francis continues saying that “For Christians, all the creatures of the material universe find their true meaning in [Jesus Christ,] the incarnate Word, for the Son of God has incorporated in his person part of the material world, planting in it a seed of definitive transformation” (*LS* 164)

To conclude, mercy is a key concept to approach Pope Francis’ understanding of Christology, and his Christology which is better understood in the context of the Trinitarian Theology informs his Ecclesiology. As the Trinity is always at work, his Christology has a pastoral focus rather than a theoretical one. Jesus' fundamental question “[...] who do you say that I am?”

(Matthew 16:15) is crucial for Pope Francis' Christology. Many have tried to give a response that flows from their own knowledge and experience of God. Simon Peter did his best when he says, "You are the *Messiah*, the Son of the living God." For Pope Francis, Jesus is essentially mercy (the one who reveals to us the merciful face of God). From my personal knowledge and experience, Jesus is the one that many might find (myself personally) in the face of many others such as those who are dying, mourning, grieving and/or living, smiling, laughing, etc.). He reveals himself to us as "The Way", that is, the one that shows how to understand contrasting and even conflicting realities and learn to live with them, as in him everything is united³⁶. As the master *par excellence*, may Jesus "Teach us to discover the worth of each thing [even that of the wild life of animal kingdom], to be filled with awe and contemplation, and to recognize that we are profoundly united with every creature as we journey towards your infinite light." (LS 246)

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³⁶ I want to refer particularly to Michael Moynahan's text "Litany of Contradictory Things" inspired by Jesus' command to the disciples "Let them (the wheat and the weeds) grow together until the harvest" (Matthew 13:30), In: Michael Harter (ed.). *Hearts on fire: Praying with Jesuits* (Chicago: Loyola Press, 2005), 160-163.

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The relevance of Pope Francis' socio-ecological thoughts for Ecclesiology

“I prefer a Church which is bruised, hurting and dirty because it has been out on the streets, rather than a Church which is unhealthy from being confined from clinging to its own security. I do not want a Church concerned with being at the center and which then ends by being caught up in a web of obsessions and procedures”
(Pope Francis, *Evangelii Gaudium* 49)

In the previous essay, we explored who Jesus *is* (Christology) and what he *does* (or *has done*, if you wish, Soteriology) and made the connection to Pope Francis' socio-ecological thoughts. Pope Francis understands ecclesiology as an invitation or a call for the Church – the sheep of the pasture – to faithfully *imitate* Jesus Christ – the Good Shepherd – through both words and deeds. Bringing a fresh approach of his office, Pope Francis made a very good impression in the beginning of his pontificate. In simple, clear and precise words, Francis has openly addressed fundamental questions that are relevant for ecclesiology such as “Who can be saved?”, “Who has a place in the church?”, “What is the mission of the church?”, “What should the church do?”, “What is the best way to govern?” “How should responsibilities be distributed?”³⁷ In the light of the understanding “The Church [as] both visible and spiritual” (CCC 779), I will particularly discuss some issues that are relevant for Pope Francis' teachings on Ecclesiology.

A biblical basis for ecclesiology: Let us bear in mind one of the passages that constitutes the biblical foundation of Ecclesiology according to the Church's tradition, “For where two or three are gathered together in my name [God's name], there am I in the midst of them” (Matthew 18:20). This scriptural basis whose emphasis is on the communal (never individualistic) aspect of the Church helps to understand better what Pope Francis intended to say in *Evangelii Gaudium* when he stated that there is a

³⁷ These questions which encompass many issues have been raised by Katrina M. Schuth. What is happening inside of the Church? Considering the fact that Christ is constantly at work in the Church (people gathered in his name) and in creation as a whole, I wonder if the church has an *inside* and an *outside*. However, there is a comprehensible way of talking about the inside or within the Catholic Church. The separated brethren who are, of course, outside of the Catholic Church (are not necessarily outside of the Church of Christ). With the Second Vatican Council, the Council Fathers reach a better understanding of what does that mean to be “Church of Christ”, knowing that Christ is the One who brings people, race and nation together. See: Katarina M. Schuth. “Open to All: The emerging ecclesiology of Pope Francis”. *America Magazine*. 17 March 2014. 15-16.

place for everyone in the Church and no one is excluded. Although this obviously has ecumenical implications, it seems that Pope Francis was thinking about the variety of talents available in the Church and how to appreciate them at different levels of the Church, especially when it comes to putting them into practice. Our social orientation and activity in the life of grace is grounded in the Holy Spirit because the Holy Spirit moves us (as Church) forward in our journey with God. The fact that we constantly put into practice the gifts of the Holy Spirit (or our talents) keeps the Church active and fully alive. For Pope Francis, the Holy Spirit is the main guide of the Church³⁸. With respect to that, Saint Paul says, “Do you not know that you are the temple of God, and that the Spirit of God dwells in you?” (1 Corinthians 3:16). The Church, from the Pauline perspective, is defined as the Temple of the Holy Spirit which means in each of us (as members of a bigger community – the Church) the Holy Spirit dwells. This definition, for some, might leave room to understand the Church within the context of a personal, intimate, individual (never individualistic, *Cf. GS 32*) relationship with the Divine. However, this definition is neither in contradiction with the communal, social (and even we might say “ecological”) dimension of the Church nor trying to destroy the communal aspect. In addition to the expression Temple of the Holy Spirit, the Church has been defined by the Second Vatican Council as the “People of God [the Father]” (2 Samuel 14:13), referring to the People of Israel or the “chosen ones” (Isaiah 65:15) of the Old Testament, and also as the “Body of Christ” (1 Corinthians 12: 27; Romans 7: 4), referring to the effect of Christ’s presence in the Eucharist with us – as God’s people in today’s world (*LG 13*; see also *CCC 781-870*)³⁹.

An Ecclesiology drawn from Christology: Because Pope Francis loves deeply the person of Christ, he hopes that the Church loves Him deeply as well and has a sense that her duty is that of the disciples: being constantly with the Master. Pope Francis’s ecclesiology flows from his Christology –

³⁸ Pope Francis. *Homily*. 22 May 2016, In: www.vatican.va: “The Spirit guides us in new existential situations with a gaze fixed on Jesus and at the same time, open to events and to the future. He helps us to walk in history, firmly rooted in the Gospel and with dynamic fidelity to our traditions and customs”.

³⁹ This theme, particularly, has been considered as a complex issue. To explore more the three different themes attributed to the Church, see: Pedro Rodríguez. “Theological Method for Ecclesiology”, In: Peter C. Phan. *The gift of the Church* (Collegeville, Minnesota: The Liturgical Press, 2000).

that is, his understanding and experience of the person of Jesus Christ fully human and fully divine. Christ, for Pope Francis, is mercy, and the Church, in her desire to follow Christ (*sequela Christi*), has to be merciful (Cf. Luke 6:36). The Church is a human society gifted by the Holy Spirit that makes her capable of embracing the attitudes of Christ – “the head of the Church.”⁴⁰ Christ’s attitudes and examples are shown through many biblical passages: The Good Shepherd, the Good Samaritan and the Merciful Father, etc. Pope Francis’ ecclesiology (or his vision of the Church) is in conformity with the Church’s magisterium teaching and at the same time challenges the Church from outside as well as from inside⁴¹. However, some might see in Pope Francis’ ecclesiology the beginning of a “new Church” as some others might have experienced in the past something similar with John XXIII who convoked the Second Vatican Council in 1962. Being totally in agreement with Massimo Faggioli, for me, it is not a question of a “new” Church replacing an “old” Church, or that of substitution of previous theological models of Church, it is rather a question of adding layer upon layer that supposes actualizing the Church to the world today with its opportunities and challenges.⁴² However, Pope Francis with the help of the Holy Spirit did make a difference.

Different ways of approaching the same Church: To some extent, each one of us represents the Church in the sense that our bodies (or better our heart if you wish) are the dwellings of the Holy Spirit of God. This was precisely St Paul’s question when he rhetorically asks, “Do you not know that your body is a temple of the holy Spirit within you, whom you have from God, and that you are not your own? For you have been purchased at a price. Therefore, glorify God in your body” (1 Corinthians 6:19-20). Each of us is the “temple of the Holy Spirit” of God, since the outpouring of the Spirit is in our heart (Acts 2:17-18). The expression “temple of the Holy Spirit” originated in Pauline Theology has been used by the Second Vatican Council to designate the

⁴⁰ See: Aquinas, *STh*, III, q. 8, a. 2 “*Respondeo*”.

⁴¹ Massimo Faggioli has understood that as “important differences in emphasis and orientation between Pope Francis’ teaching and his predecessors”. See: Massimo Faggioli. “The Ecclesiology of Pope Francis’s Exhortation *Amoris Laetitia*”. *ABC Religion and Ethics*, 24 May 2016, 2.

⁴² Cf. Massimo Faggioli. “The Ecclesiology of Pope Francis’s Exhortation *Amoris Laetitia*” 2-3.

presence of the Holy Spirit within us and consequently our ability to be open to the Spirit. Through the help of the Spirit, each of us is invited to say, “I want to know Christ and the power of his resurrection and the sharing of his sufferings by becoming like him [...]”.⁴³ This becoming like him or this desire is to imitate and follow him. The mission of the Church is to “constantly go out from herself, keeping [the] mission focused on Jesus Christ, and [the] commitment to the poor” (*Evangelii Gaudium* 97) and to “proclaim and establish among all peoples the kingdom of Christ and of God, and she is on earth, the seed and the beginning of that kingdom” (*LG* 5; *CCC* 768). Since the focus for the sheep is the shepherd, in a similar way, the focus of the church is Christ (and not the world and its offerings). Pope Francis criticizes the reality of those who miss the focus and become disoriented. This misguidance leads to a sort of vanity which is present within the Church of Christ, which is exposed when the Pope says, “spiritual worldliness is a form of religious anthropocentrism that has gnostic elements. Careerism and the search for a promotion come under the category of spiritual worldliness”⁴⁴. He continues with the difference between what is God and what is not God, when he says that “Vanity, showing off, is an attitude that reduces spirituality to a worldly thing, which is the worst sin that could be committed in the church”⁴⁵. Following the Gospel’s invitation, Pope Francis would totally agree that we are all called to choose, to love and serve one Master among many that might exist (Cf. Matthew 6:24; Luke 16:13).

Church as communion: This theme was one which Pope Francis re-emphasized. The Church as communion means the Church is unity. There is a strong focus on the Church’s call to be “a poor Church for the poor”, that is, in communion with the most vulnerable⁴⁶. Like his predecessors, John

⁴³ Neuman, Matthias, and Matthias Neuman. *Christology: True God, True Man* (Chicago: Loyola Press, 2002). Kindle Location 60. Kindle Edition.

⁴⁴ Pope Francis. *Homily*. America Magazine. 13 March 2013

⁴⁵ Pope Francis. *Homily*. America magazine, 13 March 2013.

⁴⁶ “I would like a Church which is poor and for the poor”. See: Pope Francis. *Audience*. 16 March 2013, In: https://w2.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/speeches/2013/march/documents/papa-francesco_20130316_rappresentanti-media.html, accessed on August 27, 2017.

Paul II, Benedictus XVI, Pope Francis stressed the threefold call of the New Evangelization: prayer, conversion and mission and considered the latter (that is, mission) as the key invitation for the Church to “go forth” and get over her “comfort zone” (*Evangelii Gaudium* 20) or the “parameters of the membership”⁴⁷ and bring the joy of the gospel to the frontiers whether it be to the most vulnerable ones: “the earth and the poor” (*LS* 246)⁴⁸. Pope Francis most intimate desire is that the Church proclaim the good news of God’s mercy and his loving compassion to all God’s children. The Church was called to be “a Church of passion and hope”⁴⁹.

Our “common home” is our Church like our family is our Church: The expression “common home” that stands for the earth, and according to Pope Francis’ terminology can to some extent be understood as the church *here and now*. As human beings, we are called to be united with the all creation and give praise to God, as the psalmist envisions in his view that all creation is summoned to praise (Psalm 148). In order to do this, we have to reconcile with the entire creation. The Church has to be understood as the kingdom of God to come. In both cases, God is *already* at work in the Church, but it is *not yet* in its fullness. This expression has an eschatological meaning. This meaning is behind what Pope Francis says in *Laudato Si*’ document, “even now we [the poor and the earth] are journeying towards the sabbath of eternity, the new Jerusalem, towards our common home in heaven. Jesus says: “I make all things new” (Rev 21:5)” (*LS* 243). However, in Pope Francis’ Post-Synodal Apostolic Exhortation *Amoris Laetitia* (*AL*) whose aim is approaching the topic of love in the family and dealing with the unity within of the Church, there is an emergent ecclesiology. It seems that human family is, for Pope Francis’ understanding, the prototype of the

⁴⁷ Gill K. Goulding. *A Church of Passion and Hope: The Formation of Ecclesial Disposition from Ignatius Loyola to Pope Francis and the New Evangelization* (London: Bloomsbury T&T Clark, 2016). Kindle Location 147. Kindle version.

⁴⁸ This expression of Pope Francis is used in its ecological meaning and stands for the entire God’s creation.

⁴⁹ In different part of her work, the author insists on what does that mean to be “a Church of Passion and Hope” in the light of the ecclesial disposition of Ignatius which is a beacon of light and life to illuminate a darkened world and whose center is Christ. See: Gill K. Goulding. *A Church of Passion and Hope*. Kindle Location 8759, 8848-49. Kindle Version.

Church. Family is like the Church in *miniature*, “The Joy of Love experienced by families is also the joy of the Church” (AL 1), says Pope Francis at the beginning of the document. This joy is tangibly expressed through the spirit of love and unity that exist in the family. Pope Francis envisions the Church as both collegial and synodal. *Evangelii Gaudium* constitutes the main source of *Amoris Laetitia* whose aim is, according to Pope Francis, to preserve the health of the Church at all the levels (hierarchical or not). This is a prerequisite for *Evangelii Gaudium* whose aim is to “encourage ongoing missionary renewal”. *Amoris Laetitia*, by taking into account the Episcopal Conference documents helps to cope with the frustrations of the bishops and by requesting for the active participation and involvement of the faithful believers at the discussion table facilitates greater inclusion of the faithful in the life of the Church. The document highly values and promotes the unity of the Church’s members. Pope Francis’ openness to the many different levels of the Church (especially with a preferential option for involvement of the laity that allows him to request their fully active participations and contributions from the regional and local parishes in order to prepare the two last synods in 2014 and 2015) was *hors pair*⁵⁰.

*The servant Church is against exclusion: Pope Francis’ understanding of Jesus Christ – as the faithful servant of God – the Father, even unto death on a cross (Cf. Philippians 2:8) – has serious impacts on the life of the Church. Pope Francis’ messages invite everyone to constantly stay close to the Master*⁵¹. He is convinced that the Master will teach us everything we must say and to do. However, some of the Church ministers’ attitudes often show that they freely choose not to be close to the Master and learn from Him. As a result, “[f]requently, they act as arbiters of God’s grace rather than its facilitators” (EG 66). Pope Francis’ model of Church is a Church against exclusion. In the same way that Pope Francis wants to move from the *mere* human level to attain the

⁵⁰ See: Ryan Robin. “Ecclesiological Themes in the Teaching of Pope Francis”. *NTR*. Vol. 27. Number 2, March 2014.

⁵¹ “The first thing for a disciple is to be with the Master, to listen to him and to learn from him”. See: Pope Francis. *Homily*. 27 September 2013, In: https://w2.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/speeches/2013/september/documents/papa-francesco_20130927_pellegrinaggio-catechisti.html, accessed on August 27, 2017.

level of entire creation of God in his social Letter Encyclical *Laudato Si'*, and in his Post-Synodal Exhortation, *Amoris Laetitia*, he wants to promote inclusion. As Jesus is against exclusion, Pope Francis does not want exclusion of any kind happening within the big family that we are as Church. As a result, for him, “It is important that the divorced who have entered a new union should be made to feel part of the Church [and not excluded]. “They are not excommunicated” and they should not be treated as such, since they remain part of the ecclesial community” (AL 243). This example is only one among many other examples. He continues saying that,

[Such] situations “require careful discernment and respectful accompaniment. Language or conduct that might lead them to feel discriminated against should be avoided, and they should be encouraged to participate in the life of the community. The Christian community’s care of such persons is not to be considered a weakening of its faith and testimony to the indissolubility of marriage; rather, such care is a particular expression of its charity.

To conclude, after discussing some issues that are relevant for Pope Francis’ Ecclesiology, we can deduce that there is a place for everyone in the Church. No matter who you are – divorced persons, women, lay people, LGBT, etc. – and what you do, God has mercy on you and he loves you. No more condemnation, no more judgment, for God is infinite mercy. Because God reveals himself as mercy through the person of Christ, the Church, in her turn, is invited to be merciful. Like Jesus says of the birds of the air, he says to everyone in the Church that “not one of [you] is forgotten before God” (Luke 12:6) and “the hairs of your head have all been counted. Do not be afraid. You are worth more than many sparrows (Luke 12:7; Matthew 10:30). Definitively, Pope Francis’ ecclesiology is inclusive and is oriented towards the underprivileged ones, knowing that “Everyone can share in some way in the life of the church; everyone can be part of the community, nor should the doors of the sacraments be closed for simply any reason” (*Evangelli Gaudium* 47)⁵².

⁵² According to Schuth, it is in his most comprehensive document so far, the Apostolic Exhortation *Evangeli Gaudium* or “The Joy of the Gospel,” Pope Francis addresses diverse topics of vital concern to the church. Beginning with some

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basic elements of ecclesiology, he assures people that all can be saved and all have a place in the church. See: Katarina M. Schuth. "Open to All: The emerging ecclesiology of Pope Francis". 16

**The relevance of Pope Francis' socio-ecological thoughts
in the service of unity (Ecumenism and interfaith dialogue)**

“We must never forget that we are [all indistinctively] pilgrims journeying alongside one another [in search of unity]. This means that we must have sincere trust in our fellow pilgrims, putting aside all suspicion or mistrust, and turn our gaze to what we are all seeking: the radiant peace of God’s face. Trusting others is an art and peace is an art”
(Pope Francis, *Evangelii Gaudium* 244)

Seeking unity – through both ecumenical and interfaith dialogue – has been among the most difficult challenges for the Roman Catholic Church. Although many Christian believers and non-Christian believers have a profound desire to live in communion, and accordingly respond to the Gospel’s invitation, “to be one as I [Jesus] and the Father are one” (John 10:30), the “self”⁵³ dimension of our human nature both personal and communal (e.g. personal interest or ecclesial movement interest) make it hard to welcome, embrace and live out the message of unity and peace. In the light of Pope Francis’ teachings on unity, ecumenism and interfaith dialogue in the Apostolic Exhortation *Evangelii Gaudium* and the Encyclical Letter *Laudato Si’*, I shall discuss issues that are relevant for both Christian and non-Christian religions.

Biblical foundations for a dialogue based on unity: The following verses of the Johannine literature can be considered as one of the main biblical foundations of unity among the people of God expressed through ecumenism and interreligious dialogue. “I pray not only for them, but also for those who will believe in me through their word. So that they may all be *one*, as you, Father, are in me and I in you, that they also may be in us, that the world may believe that you sent me” And I have given them the glory you gave me, so that they may be *one*, as we are *one*” (John 17:20-2). The Catholic tradition attributed the name of “Jesus’ Priestly Prayer” or “The Sacerdotal Prayer” to this passage. Unity in the Church is a complex matter because of division or schism that exist both

⁵³ See: The Annotation Seventh of the Spiritual Exercises (*SE* 313-327), the section in which Ignatius of Loyola refers to “the enemy of the human nature”, which is a significant barrier for freedom. In: “Ignatius, and George E. Ganss. Ignatius of Loyola: *The Spiritual Exercises and Selected Works* (New York: Paulist Press, 1991)”.

inside (*ad intra* issues) and outside (*ad extra* issues) the Church⁵⁴. The lack of unity among Catholics: faithful and hierarchy; Christians: Catholics, Protestants and Orthodox; and the believers as a whole are certainly wounds in the Church. A wound not in the sense that she is deprived of her unity, but “in that it hinders the complete fulfillment of her universality in history” (Cf. *Dominus Iesu* 17)⁵⁵. Notice that the word “Church” that usually stands for the Catholic Church is understood here as the “Church of Christ” and refers to the entire people of God. An understanding that leaves rooms for the separated brethren. From the course of the development of the Church, it seems to me that there is a shift in the audience of the papal documents (mainly the encyclicals) from Vatican II to *Laudato Si’*. We move from a “narrow” understanding of the Church to broader one. As a result, in some of our most authoritative teaching documents, we move from a narrow audience (the Catholic world) to a broader one (people of the world). A shift from being addressed “To all people of good will” (Saint Pope John XXIII, *Pacem in Terris* 1) to “To all people of the earth” (Pope Francis, *Laudato Si’* 3). This shift shows the increasing focus on the pastoral mission of the Church of Christ, that is, a Church open to go beyond division by accepting the gift of God’s mercy brought by Christ. Pope Francis’ social encyclical *LS* is in fact addressed to all the inhabitants of the planet, regardless their religions and faiths. *LS* attempts to meet the scientific community’s expectations by addressing issues related to the ecology such as water, air, climate, etc., indispensable life issues that go beyond the scope of any particular faith or religious tradition that shared human concerns including relations with God. Lonergan’s argument on the scale of values recognizes that vital value is a prerequisite to meet the expectation of the other values, specially the religious value of being

⁵⁴ According to Aquinas, schism within the “Church of Christ” is a sin, and it is “one that is directly and essentially opposed to unity [among the people of God]”. See: See Aquinas, *STh*, II-II, q. 39, a. 1 “Respondeo”.

⁵⁵ See also: Card. Walter Kasper, in his *Reflection on Current Problems on Ecumenical Theology* (2003), says that, “The Catholic Church too is wounded by the divisions [within and outside] of Christianity. Her wounds include the impossibility of concretely realizing fully her own Catholicity in the situation of division. Several aspects of being Church are better realized in the other Churches. Therefore, ecumenism is no one-way street, but a reciprocal learning process, or – as stated in the ecumenical Encyclical “*Ut unum sint*” – an exchange of gifts”, In: http://www.vatican.va/roman_curia/pontifical_councils/chrstuni/card-kasper-docs/rc_pc_chrstuni_doc_20030227_ecumenical-theology_en.html, August 14, 2017.

united with God⁵⁶. Pope Francis' social encyclical is an invitation to "A new dialogue about how [together] we are shaping the future of the planet" (*LS* 14) and this includes biodiversity, integrity of the ecosystem, and matters related to environmental sustainability. For him, it seems to be clear that in order "To protect our common home we need to bring the whole family [or the human ecology] together" (*LS* 13)"⁵⁷. As a result, unity among Christian and non-Christian religions is a key element to be preserved. All people of the earth are called to be united to protect the earth, which is our "common home": "Small yet strong in the love of God, like Saint Francis of Assisi, all of us, as Christians [and non-Christians], are called to watch over and protect the fragile world in which we live, and all its peoples" (*Evangelii Gaudium* 216). Caring for the environment and preserving nature in all its riches unites us not only as Christians but also as human beings who are simultaneously interdependent with each other and dependent upon nature.

Unity at the service of love and peace: The principle of unity, to "be one as I [Jesus] and the Father are one", drawn from the Gospel message, is a good reminder for us that "Christ has made all things *one* in himself: heaven and earth, God and man, time and eternity, flesh and spirit, person and society [Christians and non-Christians, believers and non-believers]. The sign of this unity and reconciliation of all things in him is [what we call] peace" (*Evangelii Gaudium* 229). Through the person of Christ God is revealed as "love" (1 John 4:8; 1 John 4:16) and as "our peace" (Ephesians 2:14), and as unity whose fruit is the tangible sign that we love each other. We recognize that, "The credibility of the Christian message would be much greater if Christians could overcome their divisions and the Church could realize "the fullness of catholicity proper to her in those of her

⁵⁶ See the discussion on the notion of value in Bernard Lonergan. *Method in Theology*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 1990, Chapter Three.

⁵⁷ John B. Cobb, Ignacio Castuera, and Bill McKibben. *For Our Common Home: Process-Relational Responses to Laudato Si'*. 2015. Kindle Locations 423-425. Kindle Edition.

children who, though joined to her by baptism, are yet separated from full communion with her” (*Evangelii Gaudium* 244).

Background on ecumenical movements and Vatican II: First of all, we observe that ecumenism opened the eyes of the Council to our relationship with many other faiths in the modern world. As a brief background regarding the development of the Decree on Ecumenism, *Unitatis Redintegratio* (UR), we can notice that ecumenical movements had arisen outside of the Catholic Church during the 20th century. For a long period of time, the Catholic Church regarded these movement with suspicion⁵⁸. Political motivations within many of the movements and self-preoccupation in the Church clouded opportunities to form broader movements⁵⁹. When Pope John XXIII convoked the Second Council of Vatican in 1963, the Church reevaluated and reinvigorated unity the dialogue with other Christians. Consequently, with the idea that “there is salvation outside of the Catholic Church”, the Second Vatican Council recognizes other faiths in God and acknowledges the value of the inherent saving power of God in those faiths. The hour has come for the Catholic Church to show openness and readiness to dialogue with modern world. The language of the Magisterium had changed. Instead of talking of the “Church” to refer to the “Catholic Church”, Church documents refer to the “Church of Christ”, knowing that Jesus Christ is *always* at work in people’s lives and experiences even in the lives and experiences of the atheists who do not recognize God’s presence and action at all. At this point, the Sacred Synod was aware of how

⁵⁸ See: Conference on the 40th anniversary of the promulgation of the conciliar decree "*Unitatis Redintegratio*". Pontifical Council for Promoting Christian Unity, In: http://www.vatican.va/roman_curia/pontifical_councils/chrstuni/card-kasper-docs/rc_pc_chrstuni_doc_20041111_kasper-ecumenism_en.html, August 18, 2017.

⁵⁹ Jeffrey Gros and John D. Rempel. *The Fragmentation of the Church and Its Unity in Peacemaking* (Grand Rapids, Michigan: W.B. Eerdmans Pub. Co, 2001) 97.

important it is to enter into dialogue with people of different religions and faiths and issued *Nostra Aetate* (NA) later in 1965⁶⁰.

Ecumenical and Interfaith dialogue: A progressive Success: Although for the ultimate success of ecumenical dialogue, we need God revealed in the person of Christ as the common ground for all, for the initial success of the interreligious or interfaith dialogue, we might consider a more open space than Christian doctrine. We might start from the care for the environment among the created things in order to approach the greatness and loving mercy of the higher power (Cf. *LS* 77). For the Christian believers, this higher power is God revealed through the person Jesus Christ of Nazareth whereas for the non-Christians it could be just what Christians might call a “Christian value”: Love, mercy, solidarity among people, and care for the planet, etc. These values are relevant and advance unity and peace among people, without raising questions concerning their faith. These values are called to be integrated and lived out in our daily life (as Christians and non-Christians). With Pope Francis, I am convinced that, “Everyone [indistinctively] needs to be touched by the comfort and attraction of God’s saving love [either revealed through God himself or through Christ – his Son – or through nature – his handiwork], which is mysteriously at work in each person [each created being], above and beyond their faults and failings (*Evangelii Gaudium* 44). Pope Francis goes further to say that, “The Lord has redeemed all of us, all of us, with the Blood of Christ: all of us, not just Catholics. Everyone! ‘Father, the atheists?’ Even the atheists”⁶¹. This is relevant for both Christology and a Theology of creation: Christ redeems all his creation (Cf. Colossians 1:20). On

⁶⁰ However, Pope Francis has found ways (“common grounds”) to enter into dialogue with all people, especially to those who do not believe (or atheists). See: Elisabetta Piqué. *Pope Francis: Life and Revolution: A Biography of Jorge Bergoglio* (Chicago: Loyola Press, 2014) 310.

⁶¹ Pope Francis. Homily: Culture of Encounter as Foundation of Peace (22 May 2013), In: http://en.radiovaticana.va/storico/2013/05/22/pope_at_mass_culture_of_encounter_is_the_foundation_of_peace/en1-694445, August 13, 2017. With respect to that, the Second Council of Vatican states that “the Church believes that by His cross Christ, Our Peace, reconciled Jews [the chosen ones] and Gentiles [“the lost ones”], making both one in Himself” (*Nostra Aetate* 4).

the other hand, at an ethical level, in any event, these are primarily ethical decisions, rooted in solidarity [among the panoply of Christian values] between all peoples regardless the faith and religion (*LS* 172).

Longing for Christ and longing for life: Let us consider the two issues. The first affirmation is that “Christians long for Christ”. We believe that Jesus Christ is God and God is the Cause or Source of life. The second affirmation is that “Human beings long for life”. With respect to the first affirmation, Christians believe that “Christ is the Way, the Truth and the Life” (John 14:6). We also believe that in Christ love and life flow abundantly because God is love (1 John 4:8) and through Christ he promises us life and even abundant life (Cf. John 10:10). In the second affirmation for humanity (believers or not) life is important. For the believers, life is important and even sacred while for the non-believers is important regardless of its cause, source. As a result, although Jesus Christ can be a controversial figure for many people, life (or everything that contributes to “have abundant life”) is important for humanity and for the living creatures. For instance, humanity is becoming gradually aware that the care of the planet contributes to life. With respect to that Pope Francis, in his homily, says, “It is most encouraging that concern for the future of our planet is shared by the Churches and Christian communities, together with other religions. Indeed, in past decades numerous efforts have been made by religious leaders and organizations to call public attention to the dangers of an irresponsible exploitation of our planet”⁶²

Faith and reason relationship: Pope Francis’s *Laudato Si’* tries to articulate and integrate matters related to faith (or Theology) and reason (or Philosophy) in a reconciling way, knowing that “science and religion, with their distinctive approaches to understanding reality, can enter into an intense dialogue fruitful for both” (*LS* 62). Pope Francis’ encyclical *LS* is open to dialogue with the

⁶² Pope Francis. *Show Mercy to Our Common Home*. Message of his Holiness for the Celebration of the World Day of Prayer for the Care of Creation 1 September 2016, In: www.vatican.va, accessed on August 27, 2017.

scientific community. *LS* starts with what we can call a scientific premise “What is happening to the common home?” (See the entire chapter One) before introducing the Gospel of creation in chapter Two. This makes a difference regarding the audience of the papal writing because many who claim to be atheists belong to the scientific community⁶³. Pope Francis moves from the expression “To all people of good will” (John XXIII, *Pacem in Terris* 1) that characterizes the openness of the Second Vatican Council to that of “To all people of the earth” (*LS* 3) that characterizes the openness of the Church today. This openness has inevitably greater ecumenical and interreligious implications. In comparison to many other Letter Encyclicals, *LS* is less theological (that is, less elements of the Catholic dogmatic theology) and more pastoral or social. This aspect also has inevitably ecumenical and interreligious implications. *LS* shows clearly that reason and faith are not two different or two unreconcilable things. Rather, they are, as our Saint Pope John Paul II would say, like the two wings of the same bird: the human spirit that longs for truth. As reason and faith are not two isolated realities, there is no question of “black and white”. John Paul II puts it in that way, “Faith and reason are like two wings on which the human spirit rises to the contemplation of truth; and God has placed in the human heart a desire to know the truth—in a word, to know himself—so that, by knowing and loving God, men and women may also come to the fullness of truth about themselves” (*Fides et Ratio* 1).

To conclude, fulfilling the longing for unity within the “Church of Christ” is a challenge. Everyone (Catholics, Christians, Non-Christians and even atheists) has a crucial role to play in the task of seeking and finding unity between the human family (that is, as the “human ecology” united from *within* and *outside* of the different churches). Many efforts have been made by the Roman

⁶³ Atheists are an important audience for Pope Francis. Notice that in 2013, as a new Pope, Francis called for “sincere and rigorous” inter-belief dialogue with atheists. He did so both to counter the assertion that Christianity is necessarily an “expression of darkness of superstition that is opposed to the light of reason,” and to assert that “dialogue is not a secondary accessory of the existence of the believer” but instead is a “profound and indispensable expression ... [of] faith [that] is not intransigent, but grows in coexistence that respects the other. See: Elisabetta Piqué. *Pope Francis: Life and Revolution* 309.

Catholic Church through both ecumenism and interfaith rapprochements through which many people have a profound desire to live in communion with a higher power, with one another and with the natural environment. Many religions (Christians and non-Christians) embrace the message of unity and peace, and strive to leave behind many things that make difficult the rapprochement, especially their misunderstanding or their different approaches on the service due to God. Amid all of challenges faced by people who are involved in ecumenism and interfaith rapprochement, one certain thing is that “unity is a journey [or a process or a means] and not a destination [or an end] in itself”⁶⁴.

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⁶⁴ For Pope Francis, unity is not the fruit of our human efforts or the product constructed by ecclesiastical diplomacy, but is instead a gift that comes from on high. See: Pope Francis. *Unity is a journey, not a destination*. Pontifical Council for Promoting Christian Unity (10 November 2016), In: <https://press.vatican.va/content/salastampa/en/bollettino/pubblico/2016/11/10/161110a.html>, accessed on August 13, 2017.

The relevance of Pope Francis' social and ecological thoughts for Theology of Creation

“This sister [the earth] now cries out to us because of the harm we have inflicted on her by our irresponsible use and abuse of the goods with which God has endowed her. We have come to see ourselves as her lords and masters, entitled to plunder her at will. The violence present in our hearts, wounded by sin, is also reflected in the soil, in the water, in the air, and in all forms of life”
(Pope Francis, *Laudato Si'* 2)⁶⁵

God created heaven and earth and give them to humanity as a gift. Something happens, and God desires to save (or re-create) heaven and earth and give them to humanity as a gift. God through the person of Christ wants humanity to be co-workers with him in the redemptive work. Humanity is in process of discovering what God really wants for them and for the entire creation. In the previous essay, we explore the relevance of Pope Francis' social and ecological thoughts for the unity in the Church through both Ecumenism and interfaith dialogue's lenses. In this present essay, we shall explore the relevance of the Sovereign Pontiff's teaching for the theology of creation, giving some keys that help to a better understanding of the statement above.

Keys to understand LS's Theology of creation: I want to begin saying that the earth – “our common home” (*LS* 3) – is a gift from God. It was created by God, according to the Law, the Prophet and the Writings. The book of Genesis particularly relates that God created heaven and earth in five days, using the power of his Word “Let the be [*something*]” (Genesis 1: 3, emphasized the ongoing repetition).⁶⁶ “Our common home” is an expression that appears more than ten times in the whole social encyclical, and expresses our connection to the earth. The earth is both “our sister” and “our mother” because we also were created by God during the six-day creation and everything we need comes from the ground (which is our origin). “Our common home (Earth) is like a *sister* with whom we share our life” (*LS* 1). There is here the idea of interdependence and equality. However, we treat this sister

⁶⁵ John B. Cobb, Ignacio Castuera, and Bill McKibben. *For Our Common Home: Process-Relational Responses to Laudato Si'*. 2015. Kindle Locations 426-428. Kindle Edition.

⁶⁶ God, according to Genesis 2:7, made use of his breath when it comes to call humankind into existence. For some scholars, his breath is the Holy Spirit. See: Pauline Walley-Daniels. *The Holy Spirit: Power of the Spoken Word: Yours for the Asking, You Can Have It!* Denver: Outskirts Press, 2015.

like a slave (an object to be used whenever we want). Pope Francis continue to say that “[Our common home is also like] a beautiful *mother* who opens her arms to embrace us”. There is the idea of dependence and inequality as we receive almost all things from the earth. However, we treat this mother like a slave (a means to be used whenever we want). In both cases, above all there is a lack of real concern for human beings. In fact, creation is the common ground that exists between humanity and the other created beings. As a result, there is an intimate connection, inextricable link and close relationship between all the created beings, and this link is the Creator present in them. Because the created world tells us about God (his beauty, goodness, etc.), it is the sacrament of God (Cf. Psalm 19). God reveals himself primarily through nature, giving humanity all that they need to live and live better. “Live better” here means to live in God’s presence, as “without him we can do nothing” (John 15:5). The theology of creation flows from the relationship that exists between the Creator and all the created— not only the living and even less the human. Creation is a whole. The living and the human are part of what creation means to be, and not the whole picture in itself. This is key to understand Pope Francis’ social ecological encyclical *Laudato Si’*, especially when he argues that, “We are faced not with two separate crises, one environmental and the other social, but rather with one complex crisis which is both social and environmental” (LS 139). The crisis is located at the level of the creation itself, and because of that it is only one single crisis. The all idea of seeing humanity (regardless of *our* ability to reason) not above creation but a part of creation was already inscribed in the philosophy of Francis of Assisi. It is something that has been so inspiring for Pope Francis.

Creation in the Hebrew Bible (Tanakh) and in the NT: Creation narratives are relevant in the Jewish culture and tradition. Firstly, creation is found in the book of the Law and has a significant place. For instance, it is present in Genesis under two different narratives that complement one another: one priestly (Genesis 1:1-2:3) and the other Yahwistic (Genesis 2:4)⁶⁷. Through the “land” Lord made the

⁶⁷ Félix García López. *El Pentateuco: Introducción a la lectura de los cinco primeros libros de la Biblia* (California: Verbo Divino, 2003) 82. The translation is mine.

covenant to the entire humanity primarily through our Fathers (or Patriarchs) Abraham, Isaac and Jacob⁶⁸. Secondly, creation is present in the prophetic literature “For thus says the Lord, the Creator of the heavens, who is God, the designer and maker of the earth who established it, not as an empty waste did he create it, but designing it to be lived in: *I am the Lord, and there is no other*” (Isaiah 45:18, emphasis added). With the emphasis, we can notice that there is a clear difference between what is creator and what is creature (or the creator’s work). Third, creation is also present in the books of the Psalms (or Writings): “How varied are your works, Lord! In wisdom, you have made them all; the earth is full of your creatures” (Psalm 104:24).

Additionally, Creation is also present in the New Testament. For instance, in John’s Gospel, it is written “All things came to be through him, and without him nothing came to be. What came to be” (John 1:3). This passage and many others in the Pauline literature (e.g. Colossians 1:16; Hebrews 1:3) tells us that the Creator of heaven and earth was Jesus Christ. Through him –as the preexistent Word of God – all things came into being and the existence of each created item is seen as something unique. A good way to understand this uniqueness has to do with Jesus’ comment about the lilies of the field in these terms, “I tell you that not even Solomon in all his splendor was clothed like one of them” (Matthew 6:29; Luke 12:27). God, our Lord, is inviting us to be attentive to the intrinsic beauty and value of the lilies of the field, “Together with our obligation to use the earth’s goods responsibly, we are called to recognize that other living beings have a value of their own in God’s eyes: “by their mere existence they bless him and give him glory”, and indeed, “the Lord rejoices in all his works” (Ps 104:31)” (LS 69). There is an intrinsic value in each created thing of the world. Recognizing that, “The Lord was able to invite others to be attentive to the beauty that there is in the world because he himself was in constant touch with nature, lending it an attention full of fondness and wonder” (LS 97). God’s commandments to love that resume the all *Tanakh*

⁶⁸ Cf. Félix García López. *El Pentateuco: Introducción a la lectura*, 83.

(loving him above all created things and loving our neighbor as we love ourselves as created in his image and likeness) have ecological implications, “You shall love the Lord your God with all your heart, with all your soul, with all your mind, and with all your strength.’ The second is this: ‘You shall love your neighbor as yourself.’ There is no other commandment greater than these.” (Mk 12:30-31). Like the water and the moon, “Our sister” or “our mother” – that is, the earth – is also our neighbor and the most immediate one, creaturely speaking (*LS 3*)⁶⁹.

Pope Francis’ understandings of sin in creation: God created the world because he loves the world. Pope Francis knows very well that creation has to flow from the love of God and reflect this love. We the created beings are fruit of God’s unconditional love. Pope Francis argue that, “Creation is of the order of love. God’s love is the fundamental moving force in all created things [...]. Every creature is thus the object of the Father’s tenderness, who gives it its place in the world” (*LS 77*). According to Pope Francis, the reality of sin has to do with “human activity” that is deprived of love and affects negatively (and mostly in selfish way) the other creatures either by using them or by abusing them. Sin comes into the world and breaks the order the exists in its midst. As the harmony or order (*cosmos*) that is within creation is essentially about relationship, connectedness and interconnectedness, there is the presence of a threefold relationship with oneself: God, humanity and creation. Some might argue saying that there is only a twofold relationship: God (the creator) and the creation, knowing that creation encompass all the created beings indistinctively. Both ways of thinking creation seem to be correct. However, the first one which is the result of an act of reason often tends to separate humanity from the rest of creation. And when that happens, we could find ourselves comfortable of being above creation, and even acting as if we are gods and not recognizing our creaturely limitations. This is precisely where sin is at. In the

⁶⁹ The same idea that has been present in Saint Francis of Assisi’s canticle and can be found in: Katherine Paterson, Pamela Dalton, and Francis. *Brother Sun, Sister Moon: Saint Francis of Assisi’s Canticle of the Creatures* (San Francisco: Handprint Books, 2011) 33.

relationship between the global North and the global South, we often forget that, “The goods of creation are destined for the entire human race (not to a small group as we know that a small percentage of people possess more than 90% of the world’s entire wealth). The right to private property does not abolish the universal destination of goods” (CCC 2452). Does that mean the rich steals the poor’s possession? Maybe yes, because the idea is inextricably connected to God’s command “You shall not steal” is a call for justice as it is found in the Torah.

What does that mean “having dominion over creature”? According to the first creation narrative, humanity is created in the image and likeness of the *Triune* God, “Then God said: Let *us* make human beings in our image, after our likeness” (Genesis 1:26 emphasis added). Because of that, people’s dignity is something to be respected, regardless the possibility that a person has to succeed or not. Poor and rich people are worthy to be dignified and valued because we are *imago Dei*, and consequently, all we have the responsibility to have dominion over all the other created beings, “Let them [human beings] have dominion over the fish of the sea, the birds of the air, the tame animals, all the wild animals, and all the creatures that crawl on the earth”. Here I choose not to say that our responsibility is to have dominion over all creatures (as we are part of God’s creation or creatures), but over “the other creature” (LS 11, 67). Our responsibility toward creatures is a significant power that we have, and this power is to love and to serve God through his handiwork: caring creation, preserving nature while looking constantly after them⁷⁰. That is, “By virtue of our unique dignity and our gift of intelligence (which give us dominion), we are called to respect creation and its inherent laws, for “the Lord by wisdom founded the earth” (Prov 3:19)” (LS 69). The *Catechism of the Catholic Church* stipulates this: “The dominion granted by the Creator over the mineral, vegetable, and animal resources of the universe cannot be separated from respect for moral

⁷⁰ Notice that for Aquinas, “In the state of innocence man’s mastership (or dominion, if you wish) over plants and inanimate things consisted not in commanding or in changing them, but in making use of them without hindrance”. See: Aquinas, *STh*, I, q. 96, a. 2 “Respondeo”. The idea of having a *happy medium* was already present.

obligations, including those toward generations to come” (CCC 2456). The Genesis’ expression of “having dominion over creatures” has to be understood as a way of loving and serving the other created entities and only in that way. Because we are endowed by intelligence, among the creatures we are most capable of carrying out this mission that God entrusted to us. We are capable of considering sustainability with respect to both present and future life. This subject-object relationship that refers to the way that humanity connects to the earth is something relevant for Ethics⁷¹. However, although humanity has a great responsibility toward the entire creation of God, “The ultimate purpose of other creatures is not to be found in [humanity] but in God himself. (Cf. *LS* 83).

We are just human beings, just creatures amid God’s creative work: God wants us to be something less than God (Cf. Psalm 8:6). However, humanity wants to be equal to God, seeing him as a rival. As a result, they desire to lord over the other creatures, considering themselves located somewhere above God’s creation. Pope Francis is reminding us that, “We are not God. The earth was here before us and it has been given to us”. He continues saying that, “This allows us to respond to the charge that [Judeo-Christian] thinking, on the basis of the Genesis account which grants man “dominion” over the earth (cf. Gen 1:28), has encouraged the unbridled exploitation of nature by painting him as domineering and destructive by nature (*LS* 67). Having an understanding that we should exercise our destructive power to exploit the earth is not a correct interpretation of the Bible as understood by the Church. Although it is true that we Christians have at times incorrectly interpreted the Scriptures, nowadays we must forcefully reject the notion that our being created in God’s image and given dominion over the earth justifies absolute domination over other creatures,

⁷¹ Many philosophical schools have developed the idea of subject-object relationship which could lead to the “shallow ecology” theory (human centered) or to the “deep ecology” theory (community centered). This book might greatly help to understand and explore the issue at a deeper level: Devall Bill, and George Sessions. *Deep Ecology* (Salt Lake City, Utah: G.M. Smith, 1985).

as it was a privilege that has been granted to us to the detriment of nature or the other creatures (Cf. *LS* 67).

The learned lesson: We all (as created beings) are brothers and sisters and sons and daughters of the heavenly Creator. “Those who have a little more power [that is, humanity] has to serve a little more, without have a kind of domination over the other created beings”⁷². The Sovereign Pontiff continue saying that “You cannot be in a position of power and use it to destroy the life of another”⁷³. Rather we have to use the *power* we have to *empower* the less *powerful* (or even the *powerless*), helping them to grow in harmony with us. In order to do so, we have to become aware that, “The most dangerous idol is our selves when we want to occupy the place of God”⁷⁴. *LS* tries to show us a new way about what does that means to be human (and not desiring to be equal to God). To be human means to know our place in the world and be considerate. To be human means to be aware that we are inscribed in a bigger picture which is the ecological biodiversity. For Pope Francis, this requires that being human is to be deeply aware, considerate of all beings who share this beautiful and precious home with us. There is an interconnectedness between all and each of us, as created entity⁷⁵. To desire the common good [over the individual good] and strive towards it is a requirement of justice and charity” (*Caritas in Veritate* 7). As created beings, all “we have God as our common Father and that this makes us brothers and sisters. Fraternal love can only be gratuitous; it can never be a means of repaying others for what they have done or will do for us. That is why it is possible to love our enemies. This same gratuitousness inspires us to love and accept the wind, the sun and the clouds, even though we cannot control them.

⁷² Pope Francis, *Homily*. 7 August 2005. www.vatican.va

⁷³ Jorge Bergoglio and Abraham Skorka. *Sobre el cielo y la Tierra*. Buenos Aires: Knopf Doubleday Publishing Group. Kindle Locations 159-160. Kindle Version. The translation is mine.

⁷⁴ Pope Francis. *Homily*. 11 September 2004, In: www.vatican.ca

⁷⁵ John B. Cobb, Ignacio Castuera, and Bill McKibben. *For Our Common Home: Process-Relational Responses to Laudato Si'* (Anoka, Minnesota: Process Century Press, 2015). Kindle Locations 458-459. Kindle Edition.

In this sense, we can speak of a “universal fraternity” (LS 228). When (as human beings) we tend to dominate in a way that we are *above* all the other created beings (which are our brothers and sisters), our fraternity is broken. This loss of harmony in the midst of creature is what we can call sin. Humanity (with God’s grace) has a great responsibility to restore harmony in the midst of creation. “Endowed with intelligence and love, and drawn by the fullness of Christ, [women and men] are called to lead all creatures back to their Creator” (LS 83). This task is possible for us because we are co-redeemers with Christ, “The ultimate destiny of the universe”.

To sum up, I have been exploring the relevance of Pope Francis’ teaching for Theology of Creation, considering humanity and the other creatures as brothers and sisters with regard to the connection that exists between them. This is possible only when we look at all things from the perspective of the created beings (not at the mere level of the human). The same “created level” allow us to see ourselves (as created beings) in relation to the creator as sons and daughters. Our tendency to break the brotherhood’s relationship would result at some point in unreasonable use and then abuse. The good exercise of our human capacity in order to make the best decisions is an important contribution to Christ’s redemptive work, as “The entry of God’s creatures into the perfect unity of the Blessed Trinity is the ultimate end of the whole divine economy” (CCC 260).

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**The relevance of Pope Francis' social and ecological thoughts for Ethics
(Christian Ethics)**

“Environmental education should facilitate making the leap towards the transcendent which gives ecological ethics its deepest meaning. It needs educators capable of developing an ethics of ecology, and helping people, through effective pedagogy, to grow in solidarity, responsibility and compassionate care”
(Pope Francis, *Laudato Si* 210)

In my previous essay, I approached the creation and explored the relevance of Pope Francis' teaching on the Theology of Creation: a theology that acknowledges creation as a gift (Cf. *LS* 76). This gift has been entrusted to humanity's love and care. Knowing how and desiring to connect with the entire creation (using the natural resources without abusing nature) are graces (Cf. *LS* 200). As we constantly use creation's natural resources, we are challenged to discern the limits of their appropriate use. In these following lines, I shall discuss the relevance of Pope Francis's thoughts on Ethics in determining the good and the right thing to do.⁷⁶

The gift of creation and our responsibility toward creation: The difference between the gift of creation and our responsibility toward creation is something to be considered. The question that comes to my mind is the following: “How to be responsible to something (or better “someone”, this earth that might be considered as a brother or sister) that has been given to our love and care?” The immediate response that I find is that there might be a big difference between seeing creation as “something” (that is, “this thing”) and seeing creation as “someone” (that is, *sister* earth or just a place to be with *brother* Sun or *sister* Moon). Creation has been given to humanity as “something/someone” to care for and to love. The way we make use of creation and of the earth's variety of the natural resources tells us nothing about our responsibilities and our attitudes. Pope

⁷⁶ Knowing what we should do to move *from* what is the case now (based on the first chapter of *LS* which I previously consider as a scientific premise to the entire) *to* what should be the case in the future (based on our goals or values as human beings is of great relevance. This approach of seeing Ethics as something that reflects on the relationship between science and religion, or reason and faith, or philosophy and theology is inspired by the following article: David E. DeCosse and Brian Patrick. *Ethics and Pope Francis' Encyclical Letter Laudato Si'*, in: <http://scholarcommons.scu.edu/markkula/10/>, accessed on September 4th, 2017.

Francis in one of his works, *Sobre el Cielo y la Tierra*, written before his ascent to the Papacy, said that humanity received the gift of creation and at the same time they received the responsibility to have dominion over it⁷⁷. Being responsible for the other creatures, having dominion over all creatures (Cf. Genesis 1:28) requires us to become more aware that true ecology is integral. There are no isolated beings in creation. We are a community of beings, and all the creatures are interdependent (LS 42). A theory of integral ecology emphasizes that human beings are deeply connected with all of creation. These threads of connection presuppose interconnections. Because these interconnections are so intimate, when we mistreat nature, we also mistreat human beings⁷⁸. At the same time, each single creature has its own “intrinsic value” that needs to be respected (LS 118; 140). In order to guarantee their intrinsic worth (or “intrinsic dignity” LS 115), would we need today to make policies about creation’s rights, just as we made with respect to human, animal and plants’ rights decades ago? Maybe this will be the next step in human universal journey. Just for now, let us be considerate, sensitive and attentive to hear “both the cry of the earth and the cry of the poor” (*Laudato Si’* 49), and do our best to ensure an appropriate and timely response. Knowing why “things” in creation are so connected and what is the purpose of this connectedness are significant for our daily quest. The Bible tells us that on the sixth day (which is the last day of creation), after creating *everything*, “God looked at *everything* he had made, and found it *very good*” (Genesis 1:31, emphasis added). Notice that if goodness is in each created being, perfection

⁷⁷ Cf. Jorge Bergoglio and Abraham Skorka. *Sobre el cielo y la Tierra*. Kindle Locations 159-160. Kindle Version: «El hombre recibe la creación en sus manos como un don. Dios se la da, pero a la vez le impone una tarea: que domine la Tierra. Ahí aparece la primera forma de incultura, lo que el ser humano recibe, la materia prima que debe ir dominando para realizar la cultura ».

⁷⁸ Pope Francis. *Show Mercy to Our Common Home*. Message of his Holiness for the Celebration of the World Day of Prayer for the Care of Creation 1 September 2016, In: www.vatican.va, accessed on August 27, 2017.

(or the “very good” dimension that characterizes that day before the Sabbath) refers to the entire creation⁷⁹.

Theology of creation and Ethics: Once we can recognize that the intimate relation that exists between the gift of creation (Theology of creation) and our responsibility toward creation as good stewards (Ethics),

“Our openness to others, each of whom is a “thou” capable of knowing, loving and entering into dialogue, remains the source of our nobility as human persons. A correct relationship with the created world demands that we not weaken this social dimension of openness to others, much less the transcendent dimension of our openness to the “Thou” of God. Our relationship with the environment can never be isolated from our relationship with others and with God” (LS 119).

We are invited to be aware that we are in intimate relationship with God – the Creator – through creation (the environment and other beings). This awareness helps us to see that “each creature reflects something of God and has a message to convey to us, and the security that Christ has taken unto himself this material world and now, risen, is intimately present to each being, surrounding it with his affection and penetrating it with his light [the Holy Spirit]” (LS 221).

Longing for freedom: With the passing of the years, we have a greater sense of how human freedom is important. At the same time, we come to see slavery (e.g. Human exploitation by other humans) as something particularly “disgusting” and “awful”. However, we are not always aware of its awfulness because we sometimes feel very comfortable while being in position of those who take advantage of others’ misfortune. It seems quite true the assumption that “We have to be slaves to better understand the slaves’ realities”. All humanity longs for freedom and the best way to express our freedom is to help to liberate others (especially, the least ones: the poor and the earth)⁸⁰. Human freedom is one of the key elements of human flourishing. Being sufficiently aware of that, Pope

⁷⁹ Scott Hoezee. *Remember Creation: God's World of Wonder and Delight* (Michigan: Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing, 1998), 69.

⁸⁰ Bruce Sanguin. *Darwin, Divinity, and the Dance of the Cosmos: An Ecological Christianity* (Kelowna, British Columbia: CopperHouse, 2007), 142.

Emeritus Benedict says that, “Integral human development presupposes the responsible freedom of the individual and of peoples: no structure can guarantee this development over and above human responsibility” (*Caritas in Veritate* 17).

An evolutionary leap: Human freedom is called to be selfless. We have to move from the idea “human beings longing for freedom” to the idea (not really an “ideology”, as some might think) “all creatures long for freedom”. This challenges us to respect the freedom and integrity of creation and to be more considerate in the choices we make. According to Bruce Sanguin, “St Paul was concerned that all creation be included in God’s redemptive and creative purpose when he wrote, “creation itself will be set free... to obtain the glorious freedom of the children of God [that is, “the poor and the earth”] (Romans 8:21)”⁸¹. The children of God are many and God has a preferential love for the least ones: the poor and the earth. With that in mind, we can say, if the purpose of socio-economic life has been humanity (from the Second Vatican Council until the resignation of Pope Emeritus Benedict XVI), with Pope Francis there is a greater emphasis on the other created beings. Pope Francis might say today that the purpose of socio-economic life is more focused on “the poor and the earth” (*LS* 246; Cf. *LS* 110; Cf. *LS* 237)⁸². In other words, it seems to me that there is a growing awareness that humanity and the other creatures are interrelated in the natural environment. This challenges in some ways the traditional thinking of the Church that has strongly focused on integral humanism⁸³. If humanity (or the “human person”) has been at the heart of the Catholic teaching of the Church, there is *now* more room for the other members to be included. Therefore, ethics is no longer about humanity *alone*, rather it is about humanity in

⁸¹ Bruce Sanguin. *Darwin, Divinity, and the Dance of the Cosmos: An Ecological Christianity*, 143.

⁸² The expression has been use as part of the prayer for the earth that is found at the end of the encyclical.

⁸³ As a Neo-Thomistic, Jacques Maritain’s thoughts have been significant for the Church, helping her to survive against the rise of secularism. For Maritain, we cannot eliminate the Christian or religious dimension of the human person. See: Jacques Maritain. "Integral Humanism and the Crisis of Modern Times." *The Review of Politics* 1, no. 1 (1939): 8. <http://www.jstor.org.myaccess.library.utoronto.ca/stable/1403915>, accessed on September 4th, 2017.

relationship with the other creatures⁸⁴. In other words, ethics is *now* defined with respect to the connection between “the poor and the earth”, as presented in *LS*.

However, it is not always clear to those who rule the political system and the capitalist economy that their responsibility is to serve women and men (and also the other created beings). “I would like to remind everyone, especially governments engaged in boosting the world's economic and social assets [things], that the primary capital to be safeguarded and valued is man, the human person in his or her integrity [subject]: “Man is the source, the focus and the aim of all economic and social life” (*Caritas in Veritate* 25). However, “Man's dominion over inanimate and other living beings granted by the Creator is not absolute; it is limited by concern for the quality of life of his neighbor [even the plants and the animals], including generations to come; it requires a religious respect for the integrity of creation” (CCC 2415).

Human freedom requires self-emptying: The Fathers of the Second Vatican Council stated that “[Humanity] can [only] fully discover its true self in a sincere giving of [self]” (*Gaudium et Spes* 24). The true and sincere gift of oneself requires a sort of dying to self, as it is expressed in the Word of God, “You were taught, with regard to your former way of life, to put off your old self [the self of domination], which is being corrupted by its deceitful desires; to be made new in the attitude of your minds; and to put on the new self, created to be like God in true righteousness and holiness” (Ephesians 4:22-24). People who can empty themselves and filling themselves with service to others are capable of great ecological achievement. If they are not, they are prone to exclude the other creatures and commit sin. Now, what is sin? What is sin all about according to Pope Francis’ social encyclical *Laudato Si*’? To answer simply, agreeing with Philip Goodchild, I can say that sin – committed against both the Creator and the creation (his handiwork) – is “the breaking of a

⁸⁴ Michelet Thomas. *Les Papes et l'Ecologie. De Vatican II à Laudato Si*’. Paris : Groupe Artège, 2016, 25: «La source de la moralité n’est plus la seule nature humaine car le *cosmos* a un *logos*».

threefold relationship of a person to God, to neighbor and to the earth, both outwardly and within themselves”⁸⁵. This mainly results from many women and men’s attitude with respect to the use of power as a selfish means to dominate the other creatures. Once sin is understood as breaking the integrity of God’s creation, its ethical implications become more visible. “Nowadays we must forcefully reject the notion that our being created in God’s image and given dominion over the earth justifies absolute domination over other creatures” (LS 67). It rather justifies an “absolute” responsibility that we have towards nature.

The necessity for an ethics of conversion: Pope Francis speaks about the necessity of an ecological conversion that flows from an ethics of conversion (Cf. LS 216-221). At both a personal and communal level, a transformation of the human heart is an important step (LS 118). “After a serious examination of conscience and moved by sincere repentance, we can confess our sins against the Creator, against creation, and against our brothers and sisters.”⁸⁶ Pope Francis reminds us that God is greater than our sin (even to those that lead to environmental degradation). We confess them because we are penitent and desire to change [our *behavior* (LS 193, 215) and *lifestyle* (LS 5, 206, 211)]. The merciful grace of God received in the sacrament will help us to do so.”⁸⁷ This conversion of our mindset has to be shown in concrete, “ways of thinking and acting that are more respectful of creation. For example: “avoiding the use of plastic and paper, reducing water consumption, separating refuse, cooking only what can reasonably be consumed, showing care for other living beings, using public transport or car-pooling, planting trees, turning off unnecessary lights, or any number of other practices” (*Laudato Si’* 211).

⁸⁵ Philip Goodchild. “Creation, Sin, and Debt. A Response to the Papal Encyclical *Laudato Si’*”, In: <http://environmentalhumanities.dukejournals.org.myaccess.library.utoronto.ca/content/8/2/270>, accessed on September 4th, 2017.

⁸⁶ Pope Francis. *Show Mercy to Our Common Home*. Message of his Holiness for the Celebration of the World Day of Prayer for the Care of Creation 1 September 2016, In: www.vatican.va, accessed on August 27, 2017.

⁸⁷ Pope Francis. *Show Mercy to Our Common Home*. Message of his Holiness for the Celebration of the World Day of Prayer for the Care of Creation 1 September 2016, In: www.vatican.va, accessed on August 27, 2017.

Jesus, the evangelizer *par excellence* and the Gospel in person, identifies especially with the little and the underprivileged ones (cf. Mt 25:40). As Christians, this is a reminder that we are called to care for the vulnerable or least ones: “the earth and the poor” (Cf. *Evangelii Gaudium* 209).⁸⁸ In order to carry out this mission of caring for the vulnerable ones, we are called to move from a personal conversion to an ecological conversion: In our desire for change, we are called to move from our understanding of an integral humanism (or a “human ecology” according to Pope Francis) to integral ecology. The focus has been progressively shifted: *from* the dignity of the human person – which has been at the heart of the Church’s social teaching – *to* that of God’s entire creation through which God speaks and reveals himself (Cf. *LS* 84). “Living our vocation to be protectors of God’s handiwork is essential to a life of virtue; it is not an optional or a secondary aspect of our Christian experience” (*LS* 217). Although caring nature is motivated by his faith in Christ, Pope Francis approaches ethically technology and scientific advances without bias, recognizing their benefits for humanity, “Technology has remedied countless evils which used to harm and limit human beings. How can we not feel gratitude and appreciation for this progress [...] How could we not acknowledge the work of many scientists and engineers who have provided alternatives to make development sustainable? (*LS* 102)⁸⁹. However, there is no doubt that technology and scientific advances should be at the service of humanity and not the contrary. We might even think that both should be at the service of the entire creation. This requires from our part to leave more room for those whom we are responsible to care, to love and to serve. This great responsibility has been entrusted to humanity, since the foundation of the world (Cf. Genesis 1:28). The *Catechism of the Catholic Church (CCC)* values the virtue of respect which is one among many human values that

⁸⁸ This expression (vulnerable one) as a way to refer to (Christ identifying with) the poor has been at the heart of the Liberation Theology. Pope Francis refers to Leonard de Boff when he has to talk about “the cry of the poor and that of the earth”. In fact, although it appears to be two different cries, it is in fact, for Pope Francis, only one cry in the occurred in the midst of creation (Cf. *LS* 139). See: Leonardo Boff. *Cry of the Earth, Cry of the Poor* (Maryknoll, New York: Orbis Books, 1997) 18.

⁸⁹ See also: Reinhard Cardinal Marx. ““Everything is connected”: On the Relevance of an Integral Understanding of Reality in *Laudato Si*”. *Theological Studies* 2016, Vol. 77 (2) 295-307.

people may show towards the others created beings when talking about the integrity of creation. The virtue of respect reminds us that God entrusted the entire creation to the stewardship of the women and men whom he created in his own image as stewards of his handiwork (Cf. CCC 2415-2418). As insatiable exploiters, our biggest mistakes are to think that the earth's resources are unlimited and to pursue the illusion of unlimited economic growth. This is what Pope Francis calls the "Modern myth of unlimited material progress" (LS 77). It might look like progress, but it is not because as humans we easily tend to satisfy ourselves, meeting our present needs (LS without a careful attention and consideration to those who are also part of the biodiversity or ecosystem). Humanity is only part of the world of the created entities.

An Ethics of mercy through the works of mercy: The work of mercy is key to change our attitude and caring for the earth that nourishes and supports us is a work of mercy. If before we see the works of mercy both spiritual and bodily in relation to other fellow humans (CCC 2447), Pope Francis; however, seems to invite us to see them also in relation to our common home. With respect to that, he says that, "Human life itself and everything it embraces" includes care for our common home. So, let me propose a complement to the two traditional sets of seven: may the works of mercy also include care for our common home."⁹⁰ Preserving nature, which is counted among the works of mercy, has the double dimension:

As a *spiritual work of mercy*, care for our common home calls for a "grateful contemplation of God's world" (*Laudato Si'*, 214) which "allows us to discover in each thing a teaching which God wishes to hand on to us" (ibid., 85). As a *corporal work of mercy*, care for our common home requires "simple daily gestures which break with the logic of violence, exploitation and selfishness" and "makes itself felt in every action that seeks to build a better world" (ibid., 230-31)⁹¹.

⁹⁰ Pope Francis. *Message of the Holy Father for the celebration of the World Day of Prayer for the Care of Creation* (1 September 2016), In: http://w2.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/messages/pont-messages/2016/documents/papa-francesco_20160901_messaggio-giornata-cura-creato.html, accessed on August 18th, 2017.

⁹¹ Pope Francis. *Message of the Holy Father for the celebration of the World Day of Prayer for the Care of Creation* (1 September 2016), In: <http://w2.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/messages/pont-messages/2016/documents/papa->

With the help of God, we all are united by the hope of moving the world toward an “ecological civilization” or “integral ecology.”⁹² The basis of this hope is recognizing that God’s mercy is greater than the ecological crisis which is the result of humanity’s greater sin today. Recognizing that the grace of mercy is greater than sin has enormous implications for the Theology of Grace. Ecological degradation such as climate change, global warming, sex trafficking, slavery, etc. is due to human activity (Cf. *LS* 101). Ecology which to some extent is part of theology of creation has to be enlightened by the Theology of Grace, knowing that God’s love and mercy revealed in Christ are capable of overcoming sin, “Where sin increased, grace overflowed all the more” (Romans 5:20; 1 Timothy 1:14).⁹³

To summarize, having in mind what is happening to our “common home”, we move on and reflect on how to reconcile the ideas that creation is a gift at the service of humanity, and humanity is responsible for the care of creation. The way that humanity exercise its power of domination over creatures might be helpful or not at all. However, in order to *see*, *judge* and *act* as human persons created in the image and likeness of God (*imago Dei*), “We need constantly to [think and] rethink the goals, effects, overall context and ethical limits of [the] human activity, which is a form of power involving considerable risks” (*LS* 131). Although many might see human beings as fragile, Pope Francis sees the natural world – God’s gift to us– even more fragile and states that, “A fragile world, entrusted by God to human care, challenges us to devise intelligent ways of directing, developing and limiting our power” (*LS* 78). We might ask the following questions: How *not* to have dominion over the earth? or how to have dominion in a way that does not result to an abuse of

francesco_20160901_messaggio-giornata-cura-creato.html, accessed on August 18th, 2017. Emphasized added with the use of italics.

⁹² John B. Cobb, Ignacio Castuera, and Bill McKibben. *For Our Common Home: Process-Relational Responses to Laudato Si'*. 2015. Kindle Locations 156-157. Kindle Edition.

⁹³ Because of the connectedness and interconnectedness that exist in the midst of creation, when we sin we sin against the Creator and against the entire creation (“heaven and earth”). This is clear in the Parable of the Prodigal Son, known as the Parable of the Merciful Father in Lk 15: 11-32.

power? According to Pope Francis, the two questions are really one question: how to make good use of *our* reason in a way that is profitable for the most vulnerable ones: “the earth and the poor”? To make a difference in our world today the good and the right thing is to emulate, “(e)mulating the same kenotic, or self-emptying, dynamic of our Creator in order for life to continue on this planet.”⁹⁴

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⁹⁴ Bruce Sanguin. *Darwin, Divinity, and the Dance of the Cosmos: An Ecological Christianity*, 142.